

**D5.4 - COUNTRY-SPECIFIC IMPLEMENTATION
ANALYSIS OF TRANSITION PATHWAYS IN THE
SELECTED CASE STUDY SECTORS**

Work package	WP5: Identification of policy priorities and support for policy design
Task	5.2 - Capacity building for local stakeholders
Due date	31.08.2025
Submission date	30.08.2025
Deliverable lead	DBFZ
Version	1.0
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Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
1.0	10.07.2025	Defining structure of the report & shared with partners	Laura García Laverde (DBFZ)
1.0	19.08.2025	Draft for final revisions from contributors	Laura García Laverde (DBFZ), Valentina Vavassori (FVA)
1.0	22.08.2025	Revisions from partners	Heleen Ballemans (WR), Marco Bianchi, Pierre Menger (TECNALIA), Paula de la Sen (CIRCE), Gülşah Yılan (UNIT), Luana Ladu (BAM), Gabor Mester, Simona Baldovska, Radoslav Povazan (PEDAL), Harry Schindler (DBFZ)
1.0	26.08.2025	Final draft with revisions included	Laura García Laverde (DBFZ)
1.0	30.08.2025	Final version	UNIT

Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Europe's transition to a circular and bio-based economy (CBBE) requires sector-specific policies that are both ambitious and implementable. Building on the previous work done throughout the SUSTRACK project, final SUSTRACK DEPLOY Conferences were designed to discuss and contextualise policy instruments at national level, bridging European visions with the realities of key sectors analysed in the project, namely construction, textiles, chemicals and plastics. Held across five countries, the conferences engaged policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, and civil society to assess how different policy approaches could accelerate the transition.

The goal was to identify which policy instruments hold the greatest potential to drive change in each sector, what barriers may hinder their adoption, and how they can be adapted to national contexts. Participants examined a broad set of regulatory and market-based instruments—ranging from quotas, bans, and standards to subsidies, taxes, and trading schemes—and provided structured feedback on their strengths, weaknesses, and feasibility.

The discussions revealed several cross-cutting insights:

High potential of regulatory instruments: Measures such as quotas for recycled or bio-based content, ecodesign standards, and bans on unsustainable practices were widely recognised as powerful drivers of change. However, they were also seen as politically sensitive, administratively demanding, and dependent on robust enforcement capacity.

Essential but contested role of market-based instruments: Subsidies and innovation support were welcomed as enablers, especially for early-stage technologies and SMEs. At the same time, instruments such as taxation or carbon pricing raised concerns about competitiveness, uneven impacts across countries, and fiscal feasibility.

Sectoral specificities matter: Construction stakeholders highlighted the importance of standards and incentives for bio-based materials; in chemicals, the focus was on feedstock diversification and sustainability criteria; textiles discussions emphasised ecodesign, recycling, and tackling fast fashion; plastics debates centred on recycled content targets and restrictions on single-use products.

Context and acceptance as decisive factors: Stakeholders stressed that legal frameworks, market maturity, and public acceptance strongly shape the feasibility of policy implementation. Policies that appear effective in theory may face resistance or delays without careful alignment with national conditions.

Beyond the discussions on policy instruments, the conferences also served as capacity-building platforms. Participants were introduced to SUSTRACK's systemic tools and methods, designed to strengthen their ability to analyse complex policy trade-offs and monitor transition progress. This section of the conferences was dedicated to empowering participants with specific tools

prepared in the framework of the SUSTRACK project and to invite them to multiply this knowledge with other experts and practitioners. In this way, the conferences contributed to both immediate policy dialogue and longer-term stakeholder empowerment.

Taken together, the results demonstrate that there is no one-size-fits-all pathway for the circular bio-based transition. Instead, progress depends on tailoring instruments to sectoral realities, ensuring stakeholder acceptance, and striking a balance between regulatory ambition and market support. The insights collected provide policymakers and industry leaders with concrete evidence of what works, what risks need to be addressed, and where immediate opportunities for action lie.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ATECO codes	Attività Economiche (Economic Activities) (similar to NACE codes)
B-EPDs	Belgian Environmental Product Declarations
BLE	German Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung)
C4C	Chemistry4Climate - Climate action platform for the chemical sector
CAM	Minimum Environmental Criteria (Criteri Ambientali Minimi, Italy)
CBBE	Circular and Bio-based Economy
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCU	Carbon Capture and Utilisation
CDTI	Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology (Spain)
CLT	Cross-Laminated Timber
CONAI	National Packaging Consortium (Conorzio Nazionale Imballaggi, Italy)
EPDs	Environmental Product Declarations
EPB	Energy Performance of Buildings
EPS	Expanded Polystyrene
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
ESPR	European Sustainable Products Regulation
ETS	Emissions Trading System (EU ETS)
EU-BMS	EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System

EU-SSbD	EU Safe and Sustainable by Design framework
EUDR	EU Deforestation Regulation
EUTR	EU Timber Regulation
EWKFondsG	Einwegkunststofffondsgesetz (Single-Use Plastics Fund Act, Germany)
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GEM	Green Economy Model
Glulam	Glued Laminated Timber
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LVL	Laminated Veneer Lumber
NACE codes	Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne (Statistical classification of economic activities in the EU)
NCES	National Circular Economy Strategy, Germany
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NPK	Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PUR/PIR	Polyurethane / Polyisocyanurate (rigid foam insulation materials)
Q&A	Questions and Answers
R&D(&I)	Research and Development (and Innovation)

REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (EU regulation)
RED	Renewable Energy Directive (EU)
SAF	Sustainable Aviation Fuel
SCIP	Substances of Concern In articles, as such or in complex objects (Products) - EU chemical database
SD	System Dynamics
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals (UN)
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
ST	Systems Thinking
SUP Directive	Single-Use Plastics Directive (EU)
TWh	Terawatt-hour (unit of energy)
VAT	Value Added Tax
VCI	German Chemical Industry Association (Verband der Chemischen Industrie)
VDI	Association of German Engineers (Verein Deutscher Ingenieure)

1 INTRODUCTION

Accelerating the transition of Europe’s carbon-intensive sectors toward a sustainable, circular, and bio-based economy (CBBE) is a complex policy challenge. It cannot be addressed by generic solutions or isolated strategies. In this context, the work undertaken in Work Package 5 (WP5) of the SUSTRACK project directly addresses the need to connect European-level vision and co-created knowledge with national realities, sector-specific expertise, and selected policy instruments. Sectors of focus include the construction, textiles, chemical and plastic, contributing to the analysis of policy priorities for the CBBE transition in Europe and in each participating country. The results of this report contribute to understanding better national and sectoral realities in the path to the CBBE transformation and current priorities for its further development, laying the base for the final policy recommendations from the SUSTRACK project.

This report centres on the DEPLOY Conferences, celebrated as national workshops and designed as spaces for co-creation with national sectoral experts. The DEPLOY conferences have brought together policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, and civil society actors to discuss according to the current sectoral context the proposed policy sets developed within SUSTRACK. These include two perspectives, namely circularity within the sector and sustainability of biomass use, while considering two specific types of instruments: direct-regulation and market-based instruments. Thus, the discussions focused on the identification of **strengths** and **weaknesses** for the proposed policy instruments, as well as potential recommendations for the adaptation of these proposed instruments, depending on immediate barriers and potential opportunities in the country.

The DEPLOY Conferences mark the culmination of an extensive dialogue with expert stakeholders who have supported an in-depth analysis of case studies across the sectors under review. They follow the earlier feedback and discussion of proposed policy sets at the European level in the framework of the IMPLEMENT sectoral workshops held at the beginning of 2025 (see Deliverable 5.3 for further details).

While the discussion focused on which policy instruments could work in the national context and under which conditions, the DEPLOY conferences also included capacity-building sections.

The capacity-building session of the DEPLOY workshop aimed to provide stakeholders with practical knowledge, resources, and tools developed by SUSTRACK to support the deployment of a sustainable circular bio-based economy at the national and local levels. The objectives were to:

- Raise awareness about existing analytical and decision-support tools developed by SUSTRACK;
- Offer value propositions for integrating these tools into stakeholders’ activities, including monitoring, strategic planning, and policy implementation;
- Provide entry points for stakeholders to either use the tools directly or request tailored analyses from SUSTRACK experts.

2 METHODOLOGY

The DEPLOY Conferences were structured as interactive national workshops combining policy dialogue with capacity-building elements. Each event began with a framing session with the *status quo* of each sector, followed by the introduction of the policy sets as a basis for discussion in sector-specific groups where stakeholders assessed the feasibility of direct regulation and market-based instruments in their national contexts (detailed description of policy sets was provided in D5.3). Alongside these dialogues, the conferences included a dedicated empowerment session that transferred knowledge on SUSTRACK’s methods, resources, and tools, equipping participants with system-thinking approaches for policy analysis.

2.1 National stakeholder dialogue on policy instruments

The methodology for the DEPLOY Conferences was designed to ensure that policy options for a circular bio-based transition were systematically assessed and contextualised within national settings. The process followed four main steps: preparation, workshop design, implementation, and reporting.

The preparation phase, built directly on the outcomes of SUSTRACK’s European-level work, culminated during the IMPLEMENT Workshops. Previous steps carried out during WP5 activities included literature review, stakeholder engagement activities, and the development of sector-specific policy sets. Policy options were identified through a structured process combining:

- a literature review of scientific articles and reports on the circular bio-based economy and sustainable resource use,
- consolidation of literature review findings with case study findings with the support of case study leaders from SUSTRACK
- input from SUSTRACK stakeholder workshops, in particular the IMPLEMENT workshop
- expert consolidation into policy sets grouped under two main categories: direct regulation (e.g. quotas, bans, emission thresholds) and market-based instruments (e.g. taxes, subsidies, emissions trading).

The tailored policy sets prepared and previously discussed at the European level with sectoral EU experts are presented in the [annex](#) for easy consultation and include policy instruments as:

- Textiles: measures such as quotas or ecodesign standards, bans on destruction of unsold goods, subsidies for innovative recycling technologies, or environmental taxation of “fast fashion”
- Chemicals: non-fossil feedstock quotas, biomass sustainability criteria, innovation subsidies for low-toxicity products, extended thresholds for substances of concern, and carbon pricing mechanisms.
- Plastics: quotas for recycled content, ecodesign requirements for non-packaging plastics, bans on single-use products, subsidies for durable bioplastics, and carbon pricing on fossil feedstocks.
- Construction: quotas or targets for bio-based and recycled materials in buildings, ecodesign and demolition standards, subsidies for refurbishment, innovation support for bio-based materials, and taxation of virgin raw materials.

This preparatory work has been designed to provide evidence-based instruments relevant to the specific challenges of the analysed sectors and with special focus on hard instruments.

Building on this foundation, the DEPLOY workshops were designed as national co-creation spaces. The objective was to move from European-level policy design to country-level implementation insights. In preparatory discussions among the consortium, it was agreed that the workshops should focus on generating three types of results. First, they would highlight the strengths or opportunities that could support the implementation of proposed instruments. Second, they would identify weaknesses or barriers that might hinder their adoption. Finally, they would gather additional comments and suggestions to refine the instruments and make them more feasible in practice.

The discussion was deliberately structured to distinguish between **direct regulation** and **market-based instruments**, reflecting two contrasting approaches to policy intervention. This separation allowed participants to explore how coercive or incentive-based mechanisms might play out differently in national contexts, to assess relative feasibility, and to identify complementarities or trade-offs between regulatory and market-driven approaches. To structure the discussion, Miro boards were prepared by FVA for each country organiser (Italy, Germany, Slovakia, Netherlands-Belgium). These served as interactive platforms to present the policy instruments and capture stakeholder input in real time.

To guide the discussion and aid the analysis of strengths and weaknesses, participants were provided with a common set of criteria. These criteria encouraged stakeholders to reflect not only on the technical aspects of each policy but also on its practical implications.

- **Effectiveness:** Could the policy substantially boost the transition?
- **Administration:** How difficult and costly is implementation?
- **Costs:** What is the expected financial impact for businesses and consumers?
- **Public budget:** What is the expected cost for governments?
- **Legal barriers:** Are there existing laws or regulations that would restrict the policy?
- **Acceptance:** How much resistance could the policy trigger among stakeholders?

The workshops were also designed to ensure diversity of stakeholder representation, including policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, associations, and civil society actors. This ensured that different perspectives and interests were captured.

For the implementation, the DEPLOY conferences were planned across five countries, each focusing on two sectors of particular relevance to their national context and also pairing with the expertise of partners organising the events. The distribution of sectors was as follows:

- Italy: Textile, Plastics
- Spain: Textile, Plastics
- Germany: Chemical, Plastics
- Slovakia: Construction, Textile
- Netherlands-Belgium: Construction, Chemical

Each event began with a set-the-scene session, where invited keynote speakers provided an overview of the *status quo* in the selected sectors. These presentations outlined current trends, policy debates, and sectoral challenges, helping to ground the subsequent discussions in the national context. This was followed by the introduction of the SUSTRACK policy sets, explaining both their content and the rationale behind their selection. By distinguishing between direct regulation and market-based instruments, participants were encouraged to reflect on the different logics of coercive versus incentive-based policy approaches.

The workshops then moved into sectoral group discussions. Stakeholders examined the proposed instruments, providing feedback on their strengths, weaknesses, and comments for refinement. By the end of the discussion, participants were asked to prioritise the instruments through a voting procedure in Miro. Each participant was allocated three votes, enabling them to indicate which measures they regarded as most urgent or impactful. This resulted in a shortlist of priority instruments for each sector.

After the group work, all participants reconvened in a plenary session, where moderators summarised the main discussion points and highlighted the prioritised instruments identified through the voting process. This ensured that insights from each group were shared across the wider workshop community.

After each event, organisers systematically documented the outcomes using a common reporting template. This template collected background information on sectors discussed and current national developments, strengths, weaknesses, and comments on each policy instrument, prioritisation of instruments based on urgency (voting results), and analytical reflections on stakeholder feedback, such as sector-specific supportive and hindering factors and implications for both policy and industry.

Spain was unable to host a workshop due to low registrations. To ensure comparability, the organising team conducted a survey covering the same set of policy instruments and applied the same reporting template used in other countries. This adaptation enabled the Spanish input to be integrated alongside the other national cases. This harmonised reporting ensured a common structure of results across countries while allowing national particularities to be reflected. Together, the collected reports form the empirical basis for the analysis presented in this deliverable.

2.2 Sustrack tools for stakeholder empowerment (Capacity building)

The session focused on presenting three key tools and approaches developed within SUSTRACK, designed to foster informed decision-making and systemic transformation: the SUSTRACK Monitoring System, the Systems Thinking and Casual loop diagrams, and the System Dynamics (SD) and Green Economy Model (GEM).

1. [SUSTRACK Monitoring System](#)

The SUSTRACK monitoring system is an operational, data-driven tool designed to support hotspot analysis, country benchmarking, and performance monitoring at the national level. It builds primarily on data and indicators from the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System, while also incorporating a wider range of indicators that capture both environmental and economic performance.

Country-level performance is assessed across four key management areas that reflect societal objectives:

- Sustainable management of resources
- Contribution of bio-based renewable resources

- Environmental performance of the bioeconomy
- Bioeconomy competitiveness and employment

For each of these areas, users can carry out benchmarking analyses by selecting specific countries and years.

In addition to supporting performance assessments, the SUSTRACK monitoring tool also functions as a repository of existing knowledge on bioeconomy indicators relevant to monitoring, thus facilitating access to, and valorisation of, existing resources such as indicators, data, methods, and knowledge on the bioeconomy. It includes more than 700 indicators organised under a structured taxonomy, which users can explore and download through specific filters, including:

- **Implementation level** (product, regional, national, European);
- **Sustainability dimension** (environmental, economic, social, governance and circularity);
- **Contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**;
- **Relevance to social objectives** defined in the EU Bioeconomy Strategy;

Overall, the SUSTRACK tool complements and further exploits the EU bioeconomy monitoring system by supporting stakeholders in:

- Understanding how countries perform in different dimensions of the bioeconomy (e.g., resource efficiency, innovation, environmental impact);
- Identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas requiring targeted interventions;
- Comparing performance with European averages or similar countries;
- Supporting evidence-based policy development and monitoring.

2. [Systems Thinking \(ST\) and Casual loop diagrams](#)

The Systems Thinking tool developed within the SUSTRACK project is aimed at providing a structured approach to understanding the complexity of the bioeconomy. During the workshop, it was demonstrated how causal loop diagrams can be used by each stakeholder to:

- Identify key variables influencing the system and trace their interconnections;
- Map feedback loops to reveal how a change in one variable can propagate through the system, influencing others;
- Visualise potential future trends under different conditions and intervention strategies.

This approach helps stakeholders **map complexity**, **identify leverage points**, and draw actionable insights for policy and investment planning.

3. System Dynamics (SD) and Green Economy Model

Building on ST, the **System Dynamics approach** introduces dynamic modelling and simulation through the **GEM** (detailed description of the model was provided in D4.3). This tool:

- Estimates the outcomes of a sustainable transition at the macroeconomic level, for selected countries and the EU as a whole;
- Integrates sectoral and industrial models to assess multidimensional costs of current trends and monitor progress toward low-carbon development;
- Provides a **systemic cost-benefit analysis**, including tangible (market value) and intangible impacts;
- Supports exploration of alternative national and industrial trajectories under different scenarios, highlighting both **long-term costs** and **potential benefits** of sustainable investments.

The GEM model thus complements the ST and indicator tools by adding a **quantitative, prospective dimension** to scenario analysis and policy evaluation.

All these tools collectively help stakeholders in assessing the scale of impacts, identifying unintended consequences or synergies of bioeconomy strategies, fostering shared understanding among diverse actors, and guiding policymaking with a systemic, forward-looking perspective.

3 STAKEHOLDER REFLECTIONS ON POLICY INSTRUMENTS

This section presents the key results from the five DEPLOY workshops organised at the national level in Germany, Italy, the Netherlands-Belgium, Spain, and Slovakia.

3.1 Germany

The German DEPLOY workshop—entitled "Shaping policy paths for a circular, bio-based chemical and plastics sector"—was organised online by DBFZ and BAM on July 8, 2025, and brought together 22 stakeholders across policy, industry, research, and associations. The workshop provided an up-to-date overview of trends and strategic developments in the German chemical and plastics sectors, two high-emission industries viewed as pivotal for the national circular economy transition.

3.1.1 Overview of analysed sectors

Chemical sector

The key to the transition to a sustainable, circular bio-based German chemical sector is renewable carbon. It is conceived around three key trends: (i) large-scale electrification of core processes utilising renewable energies, (ii) rapid hydrogen uptake for ammonia and downstream syntheses, and (iii) growing use of non-fossil feedstocks through the utilisation of biomass and reutilization of CO₂ sources through CCU/CCS technologies. The development of the sector considering these trends is detailed in the scenario study prepared by the climate action platform Chemistry4Climate

(C4C) in 2023 and updated by the end of 2024 under the joint work of the German Chemical Industry Association (VCI) and the Association of German Engineers (VDI) (VCI and VDI 2023) (VCI and VDI 2024). The study quantifies that achieving greenhouse gas neutrality in the sector will require 464-508 TWh of green electricity annually and 21-52 million tonnes of CO₂ as industrial feedstock, depending on the chosen transformation pathway. The first of three central scenarios, defines a path through maximum direct use of renewable electricity of all heat supply processes and shifts basic chemical production to methanol-to-olefins routes using CO₂ and green hydrogen. The second scenario with a focus on green hydrogen utilisation and power-to-X technologies emphasizes Fischer-Tropsch synthesis of synthetic naphtha for olefin production while using hydrogen fuel for high-temperature processes above 500°C. For the third scenario, the focus has been placed on secondary raw materials, which maximises biomass utilisation through gasification to syngas and bio-naphtha production, while incorporating extensive circular practices for chemical recycling of plastic waste through pyrolysis routes.

The integration of circular practices in the sector will now have additional support under the National Circular Economy Strategy (NCES) (BMUV 2024), recently adopted in December 2024. The NCES identifies the industry as a high-emission sector, highlighting that 60-80% of emissions in the chemical industry stem from raw material extraction and intermediate product conversion. Therefore, it establishes the ambitious target of halving primary raw material consumption by 2045 and doubling secondary raw material use by 2030 across all major material flows. Although the chemical sector is not named explicitly, it is understood that this target includes it being one of the major economic sectors in the country. Finally, the NCES provides further regulatory support by enabling the CCS and CCU processes for industrial CO₂ capture under the Carbon Management Strategy (February 2024) (BMWK 2024).

Supporting this transformation infrastructure, the "Netzwerk Grüne Chemie Ost" launched in May 2025, creates Germany's most advanced regional innovation ecosystem, integrating excellence research centres across five eastern federal states to scale sustainable chemistry technologies from laboratory to industrial application.

Finally, the recently presented action plan by the Commission for the chemical sector provides additional impulse and it is expected to push current developments in Germany. The action plan aims to bolster competitiveness and circularity, with specific trade defence measures, fiscal incentives, and targeted restrictions on hazardous PFAS emissions (allowing exceptions where alternatives are unavailable). A notable feature of the action plan is its focus on fiscal incentives and tax measures to stimulate demand for clean chemicals, as well as its integration with ongoing efforts to simplify regulation for industry (European Commission 2025a).

The plan is accompanied by a simplification package, the so-called 6th Omnibus. This is designed to reduce bureaucracy for industry and streamline compliance with evolving EU chemicals legislation. It entails simplifying hazardous chemical labelling rules, clarifying cosmetic regulations at the EU level, and easing registration for fertilising products. These regulatory reforms are projected to lower industry costs by at least €363 million annually (European Commission 2025b).

Plastic sector

Concerns over plastic pollution, particularly the contamination of oceans, have pushed the topic of plastics to the forefront of both German and European political agendas. In early 2018, the EU introduced its Plastics Strategy aimed at boosting recycling, preventing plastic from entering the

environment, and reducing CO₂ emissions from plastic production and disposal. This strategy set a non-binding goal for all plastic packaging to be 100% recyclable by 2030. As part of this, the EU implemented binding measures, such as the Single-Use Plastics Directive, which banned items like plastic straws starting in 2021. The EU also began restricting intentionally added microplastics under the REACH regulation.

With the introduction of the European Green Deal in 2019, the EU's environmental policy gained new momentum. The central goals now include achieving climate neutrality by 2050 and decoupling economic growth from resource consumption. In response, the European Commission presented a new Circular Economy Action Plan in the spring of 2020, which addresses plastics and packaging as resource-intensive value chains. The Commission announced its intention to propose mandatory requirements for the use of recycled plastic content in certain products. Furthermore, the Ecodesign Directive is set to include rules on the circularity of products. The European Council also decided in July 2020 to introduce a tax on non-recycled plastic waste, effective from early 2021.

While Germany's waste management laws are heavily influenced by the EU, they sometimes go further than European requirements. For example, Germany has had a ban on landfilling untreated municipal waste since 2005. The country doesn't have a specific "plastic law," but the collection and recycling of plastics are primarily regulated by the Circular Economy Act and the Packaging Act. The Packaging Act, which replaced the previous ordinance in 2019, sets ambitious recycling targets, requiring 63% of plastic packaging to be recycled by 2022. The "Einwegkunststofffondsgesetz" (EWKFondsG), a German law announced on May 11, 2023, is another key policy. It implements Article 8 of the EU's Single-Use Plastics Directive. This law creates a Single-Use Plastics Fund, which shifts the financial responsibility for certain single-use plastic products from the public to the manufacturers. The fund's resources are used to cover the costs of waste management in public collection systems, as well as cleaning and public awareness measures. The law applies to a specific list of products, including food containers, beverage cups, wet wipes, balloons, and tobacco products with filters. Manufacturers of these items are obligated to register with the German Environment Agency and contribute financially to the fund. While these efforts exist, academic literature points out that there are still regulatory gaps, especially concerning waste prevention, which despite being the most environmentally friendly option, remains a neglected area (Mederake et al. 2020).

3.1.2 Strengths and weaknesses of policy instruments identified by stakeholders

Feedback received from workshop participants is presented below for each sector.

Chemical sector

Chemical Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders discussed the introduction of a *quota for non-fossil feedstock shares* in chemicals production—leading to a phase-out of fossil feedstocks by 2050. Their feedback emphasised that if quotas are to be implemented, it is desirable to regulate them only in general terms for biomass (i.e., not with complicated regulations according to the type of biomass as in REDII). The focus should be on providing biomass at a low cost. In addition, market-based approaches (such as increasing the cost of fossil fuels and subsidising biogenic fuels) are seen as a priority. There was also a reference to designing the ramp-up similarly to the SAF mandate.

Stakeholders noted that *sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota* (e.g., following the EU Renewable Materials Directive or Renewable Energy Directive) raise questions about effectiveness in an international context: “Will limiting biomass lead to more imports of (among other things) bio-based chemicals?”. For sustainability criteria in the sense of REDII, they pointed out that the effectiveness is currently in question—see, for example, the reclassification of palm oil. Enforcement and bureaucracy are considered high, with significant costs due to certification. On the public budget side, implementation involves high costs for downstream authorities (e.g., BLE). There is a fundamental question about whether sustainability should be ensured at the product level (type of biomass and upper limits) or at the higher EU level, which would require better biomass monitoring. The focus, they noted, should be on redirecting existing uses (and land consumption, including for food/feed). A participant from a research institute highlighted that the current land consumption of 2.4 million hectares for the EU as a whole (for chemicals) is not particularly high.

Regarding circularity, stakeholders highlighted the need for an *innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products* according to the EU Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework and for decontamination technologies. The introduction of thresholds for key substances of concern in products that inhibit reuse and recycling was viewed as a key regulatory task. The extension of REACH criteria for chemicals permission, so that recycling and reuse of products are considered, was thought to be only relevant if the end product is actually recyclable; otherwise, a general prohibition would have little effect. Additionally, extending the EU SCIP database to chemicals inhibiting circularity was discussed as a step toward improving transparency and supporting compliance.

Chemical Sector – Mixed policy approach (Biomass/GHG reduction Factsheet)

Stakeholders’ feedback emphasised the combined benefit of product subsidies for non-fossil chemicals (for example, “green VAT” or reduced Value-Added Tax) in hybrid policy packages. Hybrid policy measures can be combined to create predictability or certainty (a “regulatory corridor”) and achieve cost efficiency. However, it was observed that products usually consist of more than one type of plastic, and currently, there are no mixed sales taxes. Other comments called for a phase-out of fossil feedstocks, leading to a final ban by 2050, as a long-term guiding signal.

On sustainability criteria for biomass linked to product subsidies, stakeholders reiterated that their concerns are the same as those noted for direct regulation instruments: significant administrative and financial burdens, feasibility concerns, and implementation challenges due to the need for certification and oversight.

Chemical Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Specific mention was made of additional *innovation subsidies* for the development and market penetration of non-fossil chemicals, including biotechnologies. It was highlighted that market-based approaches, such as increasing the cost of fossil fuels and subsidising biogenic fuels, are seen as a priority. Such subsidies should allow integration with existing measures beyond the chemical sector, and, if properly designed, can prevent overuse of biomass resources by ensuring appropriate distribution between sectors. Allowing subsidies for biotechnologies as part of structural support measures in regions affected by the phase-out of coal was viewed positively.

The introduction of a *carbon tax for fossil feedstocks* in chemical production and for low-value biomass uses was discussed as a way to integrate the regulation of the distribution of biomass between energy and material uses. However, it was acknowledged that this approach would require additional instruments to limit total biomass utilisation and guard against unintended consequences.

Stakeholders also supported the concept of an *innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products* under the EU-SSbD framework, as well as for decontamination technologies, in the circularity context. A pollution tax on key substances of concern (such as lead, PFAS, flame retardants) that pose major risks to health or the environment and thus inhibit circularity was introduced as a viable market-based incentive.

Plastic sector

Plastic Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders discussed the instrument of a *product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic* final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria, with the explicit aim of promoting the sequestration of biogenic carbon. However, they flagged that a weakness of this instrument is that the mass balance approach it relies on does not guarantee a direct replacement of fossil-based materials with bio-based or recycled alternatives.

“this opens the door to potential fraud and challenges the credibility of the transformation.”

Recommendations included establishing sustainability indicators for research funding and implementing a quota for biomass content in products.

For *sustainability criteria governing eligibility for product subsidies* with an additional cap for share of total quantity of biomass—such as mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, and restriction to durable products—stakeholders said that verifiability and feasibility of audits are a significant concern. The practical implementation of oversight mechanisms and ensuring compliance with sustainability criteria could pose major challenges. The use of caps on available resources creates uncertainty for market participants regarding long-term supply, potentially contradicting policy objectives of future growth and economies of scale. This uncertainty is compounded by competition between the push for more efficient production methods and potential raw material scarcity, making the policy less attractive and possibly less effective. Integrating farmers who must comply with sustainability criteria also presents potential resistance and implementation challenges. Stakeholders recommended that sustainability criteria must be harmonised for the whole EU.

A *quota for the use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics* (e.g., for waste streams such as cars, electrical devices, etc.) was highlighted, and the importance of allowing cross-border recycled material flows was noted.

Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products, aimed at improving the ease of repair and recycling, were praised for their potential to drive a paradigm shift in the plastics sector, especially for packaging. Stakeholders noted that “binding specifications for the recyclability of products (e.g., regarding minimising the use of additives, composite materials, etc.) have great potential for a paradigm shift in the plastics sector, especially for packaging.” They advised that ecodesign criteria are being defined in, for example, EN 45557, and that synergies between standards and regulations must be drawn so that ecodesign criteria are harmonised.

Public procurement was seen as a powerful tool to drive demand for sustainable products, incentivising production. By establishing clear sustainability criteria—such as a 50% recycled plastic quota—such a policy directly influences both the volume and pricing of sustainable goods, providing a reliable market signal and fostering a more sustainable supply chain.

Product bans for additional single-use and short-life plastic products, where sustainable and low-cost alternatives (including reuse and repair) are available, were discussed. Stakeholders cautioned, “Bans can only be applied in a targeted and clearly defined manner.” The risk was highlighted that resourceful market actors may develop substitute products that circumvent the ban, thus challenging the effectiveness and environmental benefit of the measure. Further, the lack of a clear framework for defining criteria for a ban may result in disproportionate regulation of products with minimal environmental impact, misallocating resources and creating the perception of action without significant environmental gains. High risk of public acceptance problems was also noted. Therefore, bans should be applied reasonably and only in highly targeted cases.

Plastic Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders considered *innovation subsidies for new bioplastics technologies* and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration. While supportive of the policy concept, they pointed out that the scaling of innovative solutions is often challenging, making this instrument risky. *Innovation subsidies* for new technologies, practices, and products connected to the reuse, repair, or recycling of non-packaging plastics were identified as having a key strength: “the ability to foster the development of new recycling infrastructures within Germany and the EU.” By promoting domestic and regional processing capabilities, this policy creates a strategic alternative to reliance on existing recycling industries in the Far East.

A *carbon tax* was also discussed for emissions from low-value biomass uses, such as from bioenergy and single-use or non-durable bioplastic products, to discourage unsustainable practices.

The introduction of a *carbon price for the use of fossil feedstocks* as a production input—applied to producers of non-packaging plastics—was tied to the Emissions Trading System 2 (ETS 2), with stakeholders recommending close coordination. Specifically, if waste incineration is included in ETS 2, the financial incentive to increase recycling rates would be in place, making incineration more expensive. Policymakers should therefore design the carbon price to complement, not duplicate, ETS 2 incentives to maximise effectiveness and avoid redundant or contradictory measures.

3.1.3 Prioritisation and implications for policy

During the voting exercise, stakeholders in Germany identified the following policy instruments as the most urgent for advancing circular and bio-based transitions in the chemical and plastic sectors:

Table 1. Prioritisation of policy instruments in Germany for the bio-based transition in the chemical and plastic sectors

Chemical sector	Plastic sector
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Materials Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) (5 votes) Biomass/Direct regulation & Mixed Approach 2. Quota for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemicals production - leading to phase out of fossil feedstocks, e.g. in 2050. (3 votes) Biomass/Direct regulation 3. Carbon tax for fossil feedstocks in chemicals production and for low-value biomass uses (3 votes) Biomass/Market-based instrument 4. Innovation subsidy for innovative non-fossil chemicals, including supporting market penetration of novel products (2 votes) Biomass/Market-based instrument 5. Innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD-framework and decontamination technologies (1 vote) Circularity/Market-based instrument 6. Innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD-framework and decontamination technologies (1 vote) Circularity/Direct regulation 7. Thresholds for key Substances of Concern in products that inhibit reuse, recycling etc. (1 vote) Circularity/Direct regulation 8. REACH: extended criteria for chemicals permission that consider recycling, reuse etc. of products (1 vote) Circularity/Direct regulation <p>All other proposed instruments had zero (0) votes.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products to improve ease of repair, recycling etc. (4 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation 2. Quota for use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.) (4 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation 3. Product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria (3 votes) Biomass/Direct regulation 4. Sustainability criteria for receiving the product subsidy, e.g. mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc. (3 votes) Biomass/Direct regulation 5. Innovation subsidy for new technologies, practices and products connected to the reuse, repair or recycling etc. of non-packaging plastics (2 votes) Circularity/ Market-based instrument 6. Carbon price for use of fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics (2 votes) Circularity/ Market-based instrument 7. Public procurement (2 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation 8. Innovation subsidy for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration (1 vote) Biomass/ Market-based instrument 9. Carbon tax on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use/ non-durable bioplastics products (1 vote) Biomass/ Market-based instrument

From the voting of workshop participants, a preference for enabling, criteria-based, and fiscal instruments is perceived. German stakeholders prioritised sustainability criteria, quotas, carbon/fiscal instruments, and innovation subsidies over outright bans or highly prescriptive tools. There is a clear demand for policy mixes that combine regulatory ambition (quotas, sustainability requirements) with incentive-based mechanisms to support compliance and market transformation. Stakeholders from the plastic sector highlighted a cultural caution towards bans, and product bans were the only instrument that received no votes. This suggests that bans are viewed as less effective or desirable, with participants perhaps preferring market-based and criteria-driven instruments that allow flexibility, gradual adjustment, and technical innovation.

On the other side, small companies often lack the (human) resources to keep pace with all regulations and laws, which indirectly favours larger enterprises with more capacity for regulatory compliance. This indicates a risk that ambitious regulatory packages could create uneven implementation or inadvertently disadvantage SMEs unless administrative requirements and support tools are addressed.

The discussion revealed little understanding regarding the need to restrict biomass use in the bioeconomy. On the other hand, some stakeholders highlighted exactly this need to restrict biomass use for sustainability reasons. It is likely that these views differ according to the stakeholder interests - i.e., businesses do not want limitations on biomass use while NGOs tend to put more consideration on environmental risks of the transformation.

Analysing the discussion and collected inputs from stakeholders a few hindering aspects are identified:

- The discussion around policy instruments remains heavily focused on direct regulation (e.g., sustainability criteria), reflecting both the dominance of such measures in EU policy and a status quo bias within the sector.
- While it was underlined that additional regulation is required to support sustainable bio-based products, there were also worries about increasing bureaucracy, which has already been experienced with the RED sustainability criteria. Thus, there is a tension between the perceived need for more regulation and its negative impacts on the market in terms of higher administrative costs for certification.
- There is a lack of familiarity and experience with market-based policy instruments among German stakeholders, which inhibits the ability to consider these tools as alternatives to traditional regulation.
- From the discussion with plastic sector stakeholders it is noticeable their focus remains on either technical product standards or straightforward subsidies, with less attention paid to overlapping incentives, compliance mechanisms.
- In the discussion, few stakeholders addressed upstream interventions like eco-design for reusability, designing out toxic additives, or supply chain strategies to minimize plastic flows before they become waste, although this is one of the recognized priority areas in the sector.

A key supporting factor for the German chemical sector's policy transition is the strong culture of stakeholder engagement and the maturity of existing regulatory frameworks, which have fostered substantial expertise and a willingness to experiment. The country's advanced technical and industrial base, combined with active involvement from both civil society and industry, positions Germany well to navigate challenges as they arise. Provided consensus can be built and administrative burdens streamlined, these strengths will be instrumental in supporting the implementation of forward-looking, circular, and sustainable bioeconomy policies.

In the plastic sector, the current policy landscape that rewards innovation and sets clear quality criteria for materials and products is a great advantage to be leveraged. Policies such as public procurement quotas and ecodesign standards provide strong, predictable incentives that foster market stability and encourage manufacturers to invest confidently in recycling capacity and sustainable product design. The emphasis on harmonized standards and supporting infrastructure enables industry actors to plan for growth, innovate, and meet policy targets effectively, while the strategic development of domestic recycling capabilities reduces dependence on international markets and enhances resilience.

3.2 Italy

Italy's national DEPLOY workshop, "Planting the seeds of systemic change: Tools to support stakeholders and policies in countries", co-organised by UNIT and FVA on 26 June 2025, convened 42 participants (34 external stakeholders) online. The workshop focused on the textile and plastics sectors, identifying the main opportunities and challenges for advancing circularity and bio-based innovation at policy and industry levels.

3.2.1 Overview of analysed sectors

Textile sector

The textile sector in the European Union is governed by an extensive array of regulations and standards designed to ensure product safety, environmental compliance, and sustainable design. At the highest level, general product safety and chemical use frameworks apply, but more specific requirements abound from labelling rules and flammability tests to restricted substance lists and eco design mandates. Among these, the European Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) stands out as a keystone, codifying eco-design principles for textiles and requiring manufacturers to incorporate minimum levels of recycled content. While these provisions aim to foster circularity and reduce environmental impact, their sheer number and technical complexity can overwhelm producers, who often struggle to consistently interpret and implement every criterion.

In Italy, we're currently in a rather difficult phase. Like all industrial sectors, the textile industry is feeling the effects of the current geopolitical situation, such as wars and trade barriers. Also, behavioural aspects play a key role, and in a sector like this, such dynamics clearly have a strong impact. We are seeing a **drop-in consumption**, including domestic consumption. However, it's important to remember that the textile industry does not only serve the fashion sector, it also supplies many technical sectors, which are actually growing. Considering **automotive, healthcare, PPE**, and soon, there will likely be interesting developments linked to **aerospace and defence** as well. Therefore, textile fibres ultimately end up in all these areas. Nevertheless, the **Italian industry has seen a decline**, with a **5% drop in turnover in 2024**, which is significant, especially for a sector that was just recovering from the impacts of COVID and other disruptions.

One of the most pressing sustainability challenges in textiles is the proliferation of "fast fashion," whose rapid production cycles and low prices have led to overconsumption, excessive waste, and increased exposure of consumers to chemical residues. Fast fashion garments frequently contain high levels of dyes, finishing agents, and other additives, posing potential risks to wearer health and complicating end-of-life treatment. Consequently, regulatory and industry actions target both consumer protection and environmental performance: measures include tighter limits on harmful substances, extended producer responsibility schemes, and incentives for longer-lasting designs.

By aligning safety standards with eco-design requirements, policymakers seek to curb the worst excesses of fast fashion and drive the market toward more durable, non-toxic products.

Under the ESPR, textile products must now include a defined percentage of recycled materials. This mandate has placed particular pressure on supply chains: the growing global demand for fibres—driven by population growth and changing consumption patterns—means that sourcing sufficient quantities of suitable recycled inputs can be difficult. Italian manufacturers, for example, excel at reclaiming and remanufacturing natural fibres such as wool, but they still face hurdles in the efficient collection, sorting, and processing of synthetic textiles at the end of life. However, man-made fibres (chiefly polyester) remain the most widely produced and consumed globally. Nevertheless, polyester is recycled in a bottle-to-fibre manner instead of a fibre-to-fibre approach since it is complex to separate the fibres, keeping their quality at its best. A country-wide goal could be to develop innovative processes to improve the infrastructure for fibre-to-fibre recycling.

Polyester's dominance is followed by cotton, whose cultivation accounts for substantial water use and agrochemical inputs. In response, producers are gradually shifting toward organic and regenerative cotton growing techniques; however, organic cotton still represents only a small fraction of total output. Meanwhile, even conventional cotton recycling poses technical challenges: mechanical recycling shortens fibre length and weakens tensile strength, yielding lower-grade material. Despite this, recycled cotton often enters the value chain as feedstock for man-made cellulosic fibres—an approach that valorises biomass but still relies on chemical pulping processes.

In parallel with these recycling efforts, the Italian textile industry has begun experimenting with bio-based man-made fibres. For instance, it is developing polymers derived from castor oil and other renewable feedstocks as alternatives to petroleum-based polyester. These innovations promise lower greenhouse gas footprints and reduced reliance on fossil resources, but they also confront higher production costs and scale-up challenges. As a result, fossil-based man-made fibres continue to dominate the market, while bio-based variants and natural fibres (wool and silk, accounting for less than 1%) remain niche.

Finally, cotton production itself generates significant material losses—an estimated 20 per cent of raw biomass is wasted during ginning and spinning, underscoring the need for advanced waste valorisation strategies and improved recycling technologies. Strengthening these capabilities will be critical to closing material loops, reducing dependency on virgin inputs, and meeting the ESPR's recycled content thresholds. Taken together, regulatory pressure, consumer awareness, and technological innovation are steering the European textile sector toward greater sustainability, but significant technical, logistical, and economic barriers must still be overcome before truly circular, low-impact textile systems become the norm.

Plastic sector

This is a crucial moment for the plastics sector because several legislative dossiers are being launched at the European Commission level, and others initiated in past years are being finalised. Bio-based plastics have demonstrated significant efficacy in advancing decarbonization objectives by reducing net CO₂ emissions, facilitating recyclability, and streamlining organic waste management. In particular, compostable bioplastics enable the co-treatment of food residues and their packaging, thus simplifying collection and processing workflows and enhancing overall resource efficiency. There are also ongoing improvements in single-use compostable bioplastics produced from biobased feedstock, such as PLA not only in packaging, but also, for example, in mulch film production. However, the majority of EU policies address plastic packaging, which is

reflected in the fact that collection and recycling rates of this type of plastic is considerably higher than in the case of non-packaging plastic, even though the latter makes up 60 – 75 % of total plastic demand in the EU. Therefore, the following policy options focus on contributing to the CBBE transition in the non-packaging sector.

Building on this premise, and to define policies that can support the growth of the sector, it is essential to promote recognition—at both EU and national level—of the contribution of the bioeconomy and of bio-based products, and particularly of bioplastics, in advancing decarbonisation. To do this, a key action is to adopt demand-side support measures, such as mandatory targets for bio-based content in certain applications. One example is Italy’s legislation on compostable product bags, which are mandatory in supermarkets. This regulation also introduced a renewable content requirement, starting at 50% and increasing over time. This obligation is crucial because it allows companies that have invested—or want to invest—in this sector to see the benefits of their products recognised and to compete more fairly against conventional plastic products, which are more mature, rely on shorter supply chains, and are often cheaper.

Beyond regulatory incentives, bioplastics offer clear advantages throughout their life cycle. In service, they match the performance of their fossil-based counterparts, while at the end of life, they can be diverted to composting facilities. This valorisation reduces the burden on mechanical and chemical recycling infrastructure, often challenged by mixed or contaminated streams, and lowers treatment costs through integrated waste management approaches. The distinct feedstocks, processing methods, and disposal scenarios of bio-based plastics warrant differentiated legal and financial treatment compared to petrochemical manufacturers. Moreover, the reutilization of disused industrial sites for bioplastic production can catalyse regional economic revitalisation and minimise the need for new land development. Such synergies are instrumental in fostering a broader green transition and in promoting sustainable consumption patterns.

Another important topic to highlight is the need to revise how bio-based companies are classified in the European statistical and regulatory system. Currently, NACE codes (and their national equivalents, ATECO codes in Italy) do not distinguish between bio-based and traditional companies. This leads to situations where operations of bio-based companies are coded identically to fossil-based ones. As a result, by-products or production residues are treated under the same regulatory framework, even when they could be managed differently—such as being used as soil amendments in agriculture. This lack of differentiation limits the potential reuse of bio-based production residues and should be addressed through specific classification for bioeconomy activities.

Also crucial is supporting the collection and treatment of organic waste, which is already a legal obligation under EU law, but implementation across Europe is still lagging behind. For instance, the EU average organic waste collection rate is only 26%. In Italy, thanks to its integrated system and use of compostable bioplastics in collection systems, the rate is 72%, a clear example of what could be possible with the right infrastructure and policy support.

Two recent or ongoing legislative developments relevant to Italy:

1. **The Single-Use Plastics (SUP) Directive:** This directive bans a number of conventional plastic items across Europe. Italy has implemented an exemption for compostable products in specific cases where they offer environmental and/or hygiene benefits—e.g., cutlery, plates, tableware. It is essential for Italy to defend this approach, which is in line with previous successful policies on compostable shopping bags and product bags, and has already produced measurable system-wide benefits. Moreover, Italy is the only EU country

with a dedicated EPR (Extended Producer Responsibility) scheme for compostable bioplastics: the BIOREPACK consortium, which is part of the national CONAI system.

2. **The new Packaging Regulation:** Officially adopted and published earlier this year, this revision of EU rules on packaging introduces new opportunities for compostable packaging. In some cases, compostability is made mandatory across all Member States, for example, for fruit and vegetable stickers and tea bags. In other cases, Member States have the option—without time limits—to mandate compostable materials for certain applications (e.g., produce bags, coffee capsules). Italy already leads in these areas. Furthermore, until August 2026, Member States can introduce national rules to promote compostable packaging for a wider set of applications that would otherwise be banned—such as oil containers, single-use hotel toiletries, food packaging, and more. For these products, Member States have the chance to act quickly and adopt regulations that would save them from market exclusion and recognise their environmental value. Italy already has a strong foundation in this area and could serve as a promoter of best practices. But the hope is that other Member States also seize this opportunity to fully exploit the potential of compostable products in delivering environmental, economic, and social system-level benefits.

Food packaging applications present a particularly promising avenue: compostability standards are already stipulated at the EU level and by several Member States for food contact materials. Ensuring compliance with these mandates not only secures market access but also drives innovation in materials that combine barrier performance with rapid biodegradation, responding directly to evolving consumer preferences for eco-responsible products.

Overall, bioplastics hold substantial environmental and economic potential. Their adoption reduces greenhouse gas emissions, reinforces circular waste management practices, and leverages existing infrastructure, positioning them as a transformative force in the plastics value chain. To fully realise this potential, continued efforts are required to optimise end-of-life valorisation processes, refine regulatory frameworks to reflect the unique attributes of bioplastics, and scale industrial pathways that can compete effectively with established petrochemical technologies.

3.2.2 Strengths and weaknesses of policy instruments identified by stakeholders

Textile sector

Textile Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders recognised the potential of introducing *quotas for the use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock* in textile production and imports, noting that the criteria, already existing in Italy, used to regulate the amount of renewable/bio-based resources employed in the production of biodegradable bags for fruit and vegetable, may help in the establishment of 'bio-based quotas' in the textile sector. However, the process is not without major drawbacks, as a huge administrative burden is required to define the admissible bio-based component.

Regarding circularity, a *quota for the use of recycled (and bio-based) material* in textiles production and imports was identified as supporting the creation of a market dedicated to recycled materials. Similarly, *ecodesign criteria* for mandatory durability, repairability, and recyclability standards—including for imports—offer the creation of a market dedicated to recycled materials,

with stakeholders emphasising that the rising sensibility for sustainability is fostering the acceptance of biobased products. In addition, the *ban on destruction of unsold goods*, described as an existing EU instrument applying the polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction, was linked to quantitative reporting obligations and motivations.

Textile Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders reflected on the usefulness of *innovation subsidies for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles*, as well as those dedicated to innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies (support for market penetration of innovative products). A recurring critique was the lack of vision on process design (partial/superficial LCA), prompting as recommendation a "Process Design (deep systemic LCA)". The same concern applied to proposals for *green VAT* (reduced Value-Added-Tax on reused or recycled textiles) and a carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks in textile production.

For the environmental tax on "fast-fashion" textiles, fibres, yarns, and fabrics—including for non-sustainable cotton products—participants signalled that such an approach could generate discontent due to increased prices for both consumers and producers.

Plastic sector

Plastic Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Discussion of *product subsidies paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic* final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria surfaced concerns about practical implementation, such as collecting, selecting, and transforming as filler. Likewise, stakeholders questioned the ratio of costs versus final prices of biocompound with conventional materials, which are several times superior. Among received comments, a producer of packaging bio-based plastics mentioned as a weakness the adoption of proposals exclusively dedicated to promoting the utilisation of biomass for durable goods. In their view, this significantly limits the development of such products, like biodegradable and compostable bioplastics, that are an important and green alternative for single-use products like the packaging sector (food packaging, bags, tableware).

Regarding *sustainability criteria for receiving such subsidies*—such as mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, and restrictions to durable products—stakeholders stressed the need to evaluate the scalability of products on the market and regeneration time of biomass, noting the risk from renewable resources to non-renewable resources.

Turning to circularity measures, there was emphasis on the necessity to train public procurers about Minimum Environmental Criteria—CAM (biobased is not always known/required) in regard to *public procurement* for plastics. Guaranteeing performance and productivity is noted as important for the public procurement measures. Regarding the *ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products*, a recommendation to also implement ecodesign criteria for packaging products was received, thus contributing to the compostable solutions. For *product bans of additional single-use and short-life plastic products* or product parts, it was mentioned that as apart from reuse and repair also compostable plastics should be considered as sustainable alternatives. Likewise, it was mentioned as a weakness of the terminology of "low cost" to describe available alternatives

to products of single-use to be banned. In the view of the stakeholders, it should also include the cost (and the savings) related to waste management and environmental impacts.

Plastic Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Innovation subsidies for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration were viewed critically by actors active in the bio-based packaging segment. According to their views, the adoption of proposals exclusively dedicated to promoting the utilisation of biomass for durable goods significantly limits the development of such products, like biodegradable and compostable bioplastics, that, on the contrary, are an important and green alternative for single-use products like the packaging sector (food packaging, bags, tableware). The clear recommendation was for the involvement of stakeholders and lobbies as well.

Regarding a *carbon price on emissions from low-value biomass uses*, such as bioenergy and single-use/non-durable bioplastics, in combination with a carbon tax on fossil feedstocks elicit as well the views of bio-based packaging related stakeholders. It is viewed as a limitation to the biodegradable and compostable bioplastics. It was further noted that European and national policies as well push for the development of biobased products in this segment of biodegradable and compostable bio-based goods, as an alternative to overcome some critical aspects related to conventional single-use products. Finally, it was noted that the bioenergy sector as well needs to be valorised in the view of energetic transition.

Lastly, in relation to the *innovation subsidies for new technologies, practices, and products* connected to the reuse, repair, or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics, stakeholders commented that it is necessary to verify the entropy of materials as well as provide a recommendation for effective recycling of materials. Likewise, a recommendation for the application of these subsidies is the evaluation of the efficacy of the real reduction of sustainable impact (environmental, social, and economic). For the *carbon price for the use of fossil feedstocks as production input*, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics, the main issue was the risk of raising costs for final users. Risk of trade-off between sustainable products and costs. It was cautioned as well that products are sustainable just for some consumer groups.

3.2.3 Prioritisation and implications for policy

During the workshop, stakeholders expressed their priorities for each of the analysed sectors as seen in the table below.

Table 2. Prioritisation of policy instruments in Italy for the bio-based transition in the textile and plastic sectors

Textile sector	Plastic sector
1. Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content (3 votes) Biomass/Direct regulation Introduction of quotas: for the use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock in textile production and	1. Quota for use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.) (5 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation 2. Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products to improve ease of repair,

<p>imports (3 votes) Biomass/Direct regulation Ecodesign criteria for mandatory durability, repairability and recyclability standards (incl. for imports) (3 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation Ban on Destruction of Unsold Goods (Existing EU instrument) as part of polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction (3 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation Innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, including support for market penetration of innovative products (3 votes) Circularity/Market-based instrument 2. “Green VAT” Reduced Value-Added-Tax on reused or recycled textiles (1 vote) Circularity/Market-based instrument Innovation Subsidy: for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles, including support for market penetration of innovative products (1 vote) Biomass/Market-based instrument</p>	<p>recycling etc. (4 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation Carbon price for use of fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics (4 votes) Circularity/Market-based instrument 3. Product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria (2 votes) Biomass/Direct regulation Product bans of additional single-use and short-life plastic products or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available (2 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation Innovation subsidy for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration (2 votes) Biomass/Market-based instrument Carbon price on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use/non-durable bioplastics products. This tariff shall be used in combination with the carbon tax on the utilization of fossil-based raw materials (2 votes) Biomass/Market-based instrument 4. Innovation subsidy for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics (1 vote) Circularity/Market-based instrument 5. Sustainability criteria for receiving the product subsidy. E.g., mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc. Biomass/Direct regulation (1 vote)</p>
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During the DEPLOY workshop on textiles, industry representatives and trade associations voiced the strongest reactions. They were particularly wary of quotas mandating minimum shares of bio-based and recycled feedstocks, and of an environmental tax on “fast fashion.” Concerns centred on the significant administrative burden these measures would impose—tracking, reporting, and verification requirements were seen as complex and costly. Some stakeholders also expressed frustration with the perceived “abstract” nature of EU-level rules, arguing that the sheer number and technical detail of ESPR criteria made compliance feel disconnected from on-the-ground realities.

In the plastics discussion, NGOs and innovative-product manufacturers were most vocal in favour of subsidies for bioplastic R&D and public procurement of durable bio-based products. Conversely, polymer producers and some industry groups pushed back strongly against proposed carbon pricing on low-value biomass uses (e.g., non-durable compostables), warning that such taxes would unfairly penalise green alternatives to petroleum-based single-use plastics. Debate often hinged on whether taxation risked undermining the nascent bioplastics market. Single-use products which were not in the scope of SUSTRACK, were still mentioned due to their unique properties to their contents (i.e. shelf-life and hygienic safety for food packaging). Moreover, participants argued that compostable products make sense for non-durable products, allowing their recycling and avoiding persistent microplastics release, while durable products should not degrade and would require higher amounts of biomass that could result in a non-sustainable use.

For both analysed sectors during the DEPLOY workshop, a few hindering factors and missing enablers were analysed:

- Lack of efficient collection, sorting, and industrial-scale recycling for synthetic fibres hinders the reliable supply of recycled inputs.
- Infrastructural gaps in advanced recycling and the technical complexity of verifying recycled content under ESPR further slow policy uptake.
- Systemic hurdles for the textile sector lie in costs and complexity: securing high-quality recycled feedstock, integrating deep LCA insights into product development, and navigating overlapping regulations.
- Lack of public procurement signals for truly bio-based textiles
- Lack of databases for best practices and targeted support to scale up fibre-to-fibre recycling technologies.
- In the plastic sector, the higher price ratio of biocompounds versus conventional plastics poses a major barrier - cost premium of bioplastics.
- Another hindering factor in the plastic sector is the need for rigorous sustainability criteria to govern product subsidies without stifling innovation.
- Public procurement agents often lack training on bio-based standards, diluting market demand signals for such materials.
- Scaling production to achieve economies of scale, and navigating shifting policy landscapes for bio-based plastic products
- Lack of consistent market-development support in the plastic sector, lacking investments in regional composting facilities.
- Lack of robust supply-chain mapping tools, and better communication of evolving regulatory criteria to producers and public purchasers for bio-based plastics.

The array of direct-regulation instruments—quotas, ecodesign mandates, bans on unsold-goods destruction—and market-based tools like innovation subsidies collectively point toward a more circular textile system. For policymakers, the main takeaway from the analysis of the textile sector is that quotas and durability standards can drive material circularity, but only if accompanied by streamlined administrative processes and clearer guidance. Italy will need modest adjustments: investing in sorting/recycling infrastructure, simplifying compliance pathways, and embedding systemic life-cycle assessments into instrument design.

On the other hand, in the plastic sector, the existing framework of innovation subsidies, production quotas, and ecodesign criteria is well-aligned with circular ambitions—but tweaking is needed. Specifically, carbon taxes on non-durable bioplastics should be recalibrated to avoid disincentivising compostable packaging solutions. Policymakers should integrate stakeholder

feedback and systemic LCA into subsidy and tax design, and provide clear, stable criteria to reduce market uncertainty. Italy's leadership in compostables suggests only minor adjustments will be needed if these refinements are adopted.

3.3 Netherlands and Belgium

The joint DEPLOY workshop for the Netherlands and Belgium, titled "Planting the Seeds of Systemic Change," was conducted online on July 10, 2025, gathering 17 stakeholders across policy, industry, research, and associations. The sessions focused on the chemical and construction sectors, both of which featured as key national priorities for the bio-based and circular economy transition.

3.3.1 Overview of analysed sectors

Chemical sector

The chemical sector is one of the largest and most energy-intensive industries in both the Netherlands and the EU (CBS 2024). At EU level, the industry accounted for approximately 22% of the total final energy consumption in 2020 (EEA 2023). It is heavily reliant on fossil feedstocks for both energy and raw materials and contributes 3.2% of total GHG emissions in the EU (EEA 2023). In 2023, the EU chemical industry generated €655 billion in sales and employed 3.4 million people, playing a central role in the EU economy (CEFIC 2024). However, its linear and fossil-dependent model contributes to resource depletion, pollution, and waste generation, with hazardous substances posing risks to human health and ecosystems (EEA 2023). About 80% of the chemicals produced are hazardous to human health, and 28% are classified as a very toxic health hazard (EUROSTAT 2024). Currently, over 98% of the carbon feedstock used in the chemical industry is fossil-based, indicating a substantial dependency on non-renewable resources and highlighting the urgent need for a transition toward more sustainable, circular alternatives (Systemiq 2022).

The European (as well as Dutch) chemical sector is thus under increasing pressure to decarbonise, reduce toxicity, and transition to safer and more sustainable alternatives. In the Netherlands, up until 2021 no downward trend in terms of CO₂-intensity was visible, but in the most recent two years, the emissions decreased by 18.8%, mainly as a result of decreased production and the higher price of natural gas in that period (CLO 2024). However, structural improvements are critical to achieving climate neutrality and reducing the sector's environmental and health burdens (European Commission 2020, 2023).

To this end, the Dutch government has embarked on two tracks to defossilize the non-energetic use of carbon; a national and an international track. In the national track, the challenges to transition the Dutch chemical industry to sustainable carbon use (i.e., secondary resources, bio-based resources and CO₂) were assessed through research and stakeholder interactions. To begin with, challenges were identified in terms of what needs to be done (e.g., stimulating EU internal demand, harmonising (EU) legislation, investing in R&D, addressing the preconditions for the transition such as a positive, competitive, circular business case). Then, agreement was to be found on how to tackle these challenges (e.g., how to create market demand? How to ensure alignment of the phase-in of sustainable carbon and phase-out of fossil carbon?). In the international track, the Dutch government presented a statement to the European Commission, pushing for the introduction of a sustainable carbon policy package. In the Clean Industrial Deal, first promising signs are appearing. However, the industry is in heavy weather and policy is yet to catch up.

Construction sector

The use of bio-based insulation materials is steadily increasing. Materials such as wood fibre, wood wool, cellulose, lime-hemp, and straw are being chosen more frequently as sustainable alternatives to traditional insulation products like mineral wool, expanded polystyrene (EPS), and polyurethane/polyisocyanurate (PUR/PIR). This trend is linked to the growing familiarity of architects and contractors with bio-based materials. A similar shift is observed in the use of bio-based structural and finishing materials. The move toward more vapor-open construction systems is also closely related to this development.

Wood-based panel materials are becoming particularly popular. Timber framing with solid beams remains the dominant structural approach, followed by engineered wood products such as laminated veneer lumber (LVL), glued laminated timber (glulam), I-joists, and cross-laminated timber (CLT) (Van den Bossche 2025).

Despite the growing interest in bio-based materials, several challenges remain. One of the key issues is the balance between cost and performance. For instance, bio-based materials often face limitations in compressive strength when used in flat roof applications. In addition, their performance potential is not yet fully recognized in Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) assessments. This often results in thicker insulation layers, as benefits such as moisture buffering and improved indoor comfort are not adequately factored into current regulations. Although awareness is improving, knowledge gaps and uncertainties among professionals and the general public still persist.

While bio-based insulation and finishing materials are gaining traction, the number of new homes constructed using timber remains in slow decline in Belgium. Although new and innovative projects are being planned, such as a timber-based residential tower in Antwerp, significant barriers still affect the uptake of multi-story timber buildings in both Belgium and the Netherlands. Key obstacles include limited experience, and regulatory challenges related to fire safety and building standards.

Several policy measures could help to overcome these barriers. These include accounting for biogenic carbon storage in environmental assessments, expanding national databases to include more timber products, updating building codes to better support timber construction, setting targets or quotas for timber buildings, and increasing government support and industry lobbying. Promoting awareness of the regional expertise available in timber construction, through companies such as CLT-S, Stabilame and Heijmans, can also help bridge knowledge gaps. The necessary skills and technologies are already in place, but the conservative mindset of the construction industry remains a significant barrier. Embracing innovation and change will be crucial to accelerating the adoption of bio-based and timber-based construction solutions.

3.3.2 Strengths and weaknesses of policy instruments identified by stakeholders

Chemical sector

Chemical Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders examined the *quota for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemicals production* (aimed at phasing out fossil feedstocks). They pointed out that the risk exists that implementing an

instrument like a ‘bijmengverplichting’ (in English: blending obligation) will take away opportunities in other sectors. The effectiveness of such a quota would depend on the share of non-fossil feedstock required, with costs varying accordingly. Participants emphasized a need for scenario analysis to be able to judge the instrument’s effectiveness, and stressed that to fulfil the demand for biobased feedstocks, it needs to be understood how underutilized lignocellulosic resources can be utilized. They also called for a resilient policy on promoting the use of their own residues.

Innovation subsidies for the development and market penetration of non-fossil feedstocks were seen by stakeholders as rather a mixed policy instrument than a direct regulation. With respect to *sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible for quotas* (referencing the EU Renewable Materials Directive), it was highlighted that it is important to keep the criteria simple and uniform with not too many administrative issues, ideally applying EU broad but preferably worldwide. The foundation for long-term sustainability should be a healthy soil, and regulations should emphasize soil quality. Efficiency was also a crucial concern due to the limited resources availability. Stakeholders emphasized that inefficient routes with biomass or that result in very poorly recyclable products should be phased out, and support should be directed mostly towards efficient pathways to chemicals. There was strong stakeholder backing for performing LCA’s or implementing passports for all products/materials, also those of fossil origin, with a suggestion to add social criteria to RED.

Participants suggested in general that EU policies should emphasize the importance of NPK recycling, promoting the co-production of biochar and prioritizing or even setting as mandatory the circularity of soil-derived minerals.

Chemical Sector – Mixed approach (Biomass Factsheet)

Product subsidies for non-fossil chemicals were discussed, and expressed from participants that from the literature and practice, it is known that positive incentives usually are more effective than negative, so a product subsidy might be more effective than a penalty. However, the public budgetary impact was a major concern, considering that product subsidies are costly, especially to the public budget.

Chemical Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

For *innovation subsidy policies* for innovative, non-fossil chemicals and the market penetration of novel products, stakeholders underlined that market-based instruments, which are not always regulated by the government but often rely on voluntary agreements, can be highly effective in promoting innovation. Examples cited were the adoption of certification schemes and standards and the implementation of price premiums by supply chain actors. It was considered important for the government to influence market penetration by creating a demand for such products, e.g., green procurement policies, long-term contracts, among others. The discussion of a *carbon tax* on fossil feedstocks and low-value biomass uses did not elicit additional detail in the available comments. Finally, regarding market-based circularity a digital product passport was proposed to inform future policy instruments

Construction sector

Construction Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

With respect to *quotas or targets for the use of biobased materials in new buildings* (including public procurement), stakeholders asserted that in order to boost the use of biobased materials (and in particular wood) in construction, the idea of a minimum level of wood use, e.g. in public construction initiatives should be promoted. This could then serve as an example for the private sector. At the same time, participants highlighted that the current Belgian Environmental Product Declarations (B-EPDs) tend to disadvantage biobased materials due to the way land use criteria are applied. These frameworks do not adequately consider the environmental benefits of sourcing wood locally within Europe, where practices do not contribute to deforestation. As a result, the sustainability of regionally sourced biobased materials may be undervalued in comparison to conventional options, despite their favourable impact on forests and land management. Stakeholders encouraged providing an opportunity for bio-based materials to influence the development or adaptation of fire regulations, ensuring that the specific characteristics of biomass are properly considered. They also suggested introducing benchmarks, such as setting a fixed proportion of governmental buildings to be constructed using timber structures, with 25% referenced as a norm from Austria.

Sustainability criteria tied to quotas have the potential to establish requirements for biodiversity in forest management and help ensure that wood is sourced sustainably, though there is a risk that such criteria might not be effective in restoring forest health and resilience. The acceptance of biobased materials depends on robust sustainability assurance, with EU Timber Regulation (EUTR) and EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) cited as significant frameworks for wood and wood products. Stakeholders emphasized the importance of limiting resource use taxes only to non-renewable materials, not to renewables such as wood and hemp, and highlighted the need to reduce the burning of wood biomass in favour of directing more wood towards construction applications. *Subsidies for the refurbishment of buildings* were described as valuable for setting a vision for the market and generating practical examples and knowledge, with the preservation of existing buildings considered crucial since new construction typically has greater negative environmental impacts.

Regarding *quotas or targets for recycled materials in new buildings*, the use of primary materials is not yet widely perceived as a sustainability problem in the built environment, but increased demand for secondary materials can accelerate circular demolition. Availability of secondary materials is limited, leading stakeholders to advise focusing regulations on specific material flows, citing the Betonakkoord (concrete agreement) and Bouwakkoord staal (Steel Construction agreement) as effective government-supported practices. Stakeholders also raised practical questions about who should be responsible for waste disposal and material reprocessing costs, stressed that definitions of recycled content must be strict to prevent lobbying from conventional materials sectors, and warned not to overlook the technical suitability ("fitness for use") of recycled materials. For example, much reclaimed timber is used for particleboard, while requirements such as CE-marking are relevant when reusing timber in structural applications.

Ecodesign criteria for building companies, covering aspects such as reuse, disassembly, durability, adaptability, repair, and minimised material intensity, could in the future be underpinned by the ESPR (ecodesign for sustainable products regulation), though market readiness remains in question. As a complementary measure, a tax benefit for using or reprocessing reuse materials was suggested. *Demolition standards aimed at increasing reuse, upcycling, and recycling*—and thereby reducing waste—are also seen as critical, although the existing building stock is often not designed to facilitate circularity, making reuse and upcycling more difficult in practice. Reference

was made to Denmark, where demolition audits are legally required to assess the potential for circular material use, and to France, where extended producer responsibility legislation mandates that materials from building demolition be sorted for reuse or recycling.

Construction Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Market-based policy options included *innovation subsidies for the development and use of innovative bio-based construction materials*. These were widely regarded as a good way to incentivize innovation, which is crucial for the sector’s future development. Stakeholders recommended that a chain approach is needed, involving large-scale demand, simultaneous scaling of industry, and ongoing technology advancement. They also highlighted the importance of supporting industry innovation, particularly for high-value timber products, and called for developing regulations that define strength classes for timber species that do not yet have established norms. Subsidies for renovations using biobased materials—including for walls and windows—were described as particularly important, given that renovation represents a significant challenge in Europe.

Proposals were advanced for a *carbon tax covering all lifecycle GHG emissions from building materials* not already addressed by existing emissions trading, including the carbon content of short-life biomass materials. A carbon tax of this nature would be expected to boost biobased materials. However, it was noted that current Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) do not account for the carbon stock present in biogenic carbon, so it is important to be able to demonstrate at least 50 years of carbon sink. The setting of EPD standards is seen as a political issue, as it creates competition between fossil-based and biobased materials, with land use considerations also having a potential negative impact on ratings for biobased products.

Stakeholders pointed to the instrument of a *carbon credit or subsidy for bio-based building materials* that ensure long-term carbon storage (over 50 years), making them exempt from the carbon tax, as a direct way to address CO₂ footprints and to create a future-proof, market-driven incentive. Despite its potential, the sector currently faces challenges such as insufficient market readiness and scale among materials and producers, and the need for significant financial resources and supportive instruments to foster a market that can afford to pay a premium for such solutions.

In the context of circularity, *innovation subsidies for new circular technologies or practices*—such as enhanced use of recycled materials—were viewed as less effective unless there is a clear and viable business case. Stakeholders noted that the circular business case is currently negative, with reuse consistently more expensive than using new materials, and remarked that providing subsidies without addressing this would be ineffective. Rising prices in the Dutch building sector and a lack of data and understanding about available secondary materials are also significant obstacles to building more circularly, with examples given such as DuSpot, Insert, and Madopt. Meanwhile, a *material tax on the use of virgin raw materials* or on construction (including imports) was regarded as a very good initial measure to boost demand for secondary materials. There was also a strong openness to recognizing and rewarding long-life materials and projects, incentivizing their continued use and adaptability at the end of their service life.

3.3.3 Prioritisation and implications for policy

The prioritisation exercise produced limited consensus for the chemical sector. As reported, workshop participants in this sector strongly questioned the voting exercise, considering this ranking would result in a simplified view not doing justice to the complex reality and context for

the sector. In practice, only two policy instruments received a single vote each, namely the *quota for non-fossil feedstock shares*, (Biomass/Direct regulation) and the *product subsidy for non-fossil chemicals* (Biomass/Market-based). Therefore, no meaningful analysis can be carried out of this voting exercise.

In contrast, the construction sector revealed a clearer sense of stakeholder priorities. Here, innovation subsidies for innovative bio-based construction materials were the most favoured instrument (4 votes), followed by sustainability criteria (3 votes) and demolition standards (3 votes). Quotas or targets for bio-based materials, carbon credits/subsidies for long carbon storage in biobased construction, and innovation subsidies for circularity each received 2 votes.

Table 3. Prioritisation of policy instruments in the Netherlands and Belgium for the bio-based transition in the chemical and construction sectors (respectively).

Chemical sector	Construction sector
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Quota for non-fossil feedstock shares, (1 vote) Biomass/ Direct regulation 2. Product subsidy for non-fossil chemicals (1 vote) Biomass/ Market-based instrument 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Innovation subsidy for innovative bio-based construction materials (4 votes) Biomass/ Market-based instrument 2. Sustainability criteria (3 votes) Biomass/ Direct regulation 3. Demolition standards (3 votes) Circularity/ Direct regulation 4. Quota/target (2 votes) Biomass/ Direct regulation 5. Carbon credits/subsidy (2 votes) Biomass/ Market-based instrument 6. Innovation subsidy (2 votes) Circularity/ Market-based instrument

Within the chemicals sector discussion, a general notion of the stakeholders -mainly the policy makers and advisors- was that it is quite challenging to attach strengths and weaknesses of the policy instruments presented given their generic nature. A more extensive, detailed policy analysis with different scenarios is needed to enable a judgment of the effectiveness of instruments, and as such facilitate meaningful discussion on this complex topic.

Following the above remark, the discussion mainly focussed on the biomass factsheets. With regard to direct regulation, it was emphasized by a policy advisor that currently no level playing field exists between the production of chemicals and energy from biobased and fossil-based resources. Currently, fossil-based products are much cheaper than their biobased counterparts, and strict sustainability criteria only exist for the latter (as part of the RED). This imbalance must be repaired.

Also, an industrial stakeholder pinpointed that the focus of policy support should be on scalable, efficient technologies rather than niche solutions featuring inefficient conversion routes. Resources are scarce and need to be used in a targeted, efficient manner. Thereby, according to this participant, it is essential to tap into substantial amounts of lignocellulosic resources (at the scale of several million tons) that are readily available and currently underutilized in the Netherlands.

Across both sectors, several existing barriers or missing enablers are identified from the discussion with stakeholders:

- The Renewable Energy Directive (RED) is a major barrier due to its complexity and its focus on supporting only energy applications of biomass, rather than non-energy (chemical) uses.
- The complexity and lack of uniformity in RED implementation create additional administrative burdens.
- Quotas for non-fossil feedstock shares risk causing market distortion, as they may generate opportunities in some sectors at the expense of others.
- Product or innovation subsidies for the bio-based chemical sector, while more effective than penalties in driving transition, can be financially burdensome for public authorities.
- Rising costs of construction materials, combined with inadequate reliable data and insight into available secondary materials, strongly discourage circular construction practices.
- The prevailing mindset in the construction sector remains a significant barrier to the acceptance and adoption of bio-based materials.
- Pricing and availability challenges, especially for large-scale deployment of bio-based materials, continue to restrict uptake.
- The conservative nature of the construction industry and entrenched preferences for traditional materials persist, particularly against a backdrop of high construction and housing costs in both countries.
- Many materials and producers are not yet market-ready or operating at sufficient scale to meet market needs.

The Dutch government has embarked on a track to defossilize the chemical industry. As such, it has identified the need for action with regard to stimulating EU internal demand, harmonising (EU) legislation, investing in R&D, addressing the preconditions for the transition such as a positive, competitive, circular business case. More concretely building on the results from the DEPLOY conference, a few specific implications for the Dutch policy environment are specified below.

The RED is operational at a European level, hence cannot be changed merely for the Netherlands. However, an initiative for a comprehensive legal sustainability framework is currently under development by the Dutch government. This framework seeks to align sustainability criteria for the production of biobased products (including chemicals) with those already in place for bioenergy and biofuels, in accordance with the RED. This framework - which in the first place will be voluntary - has the potential to contribute to harmonizing with existing legislation, and as such create a more equal level playing field between non-fossil and fossil energy and chemical applications. Nevertheless, to strengthen the effectiveness of the Dutch framework and avoid unintended burden shifting effects, it would be beneficial to widen its scope to Europe at large.

In addition, several policy instruments are already in place in the Netherlands that should stimulate biobased innovation, like National Approach Biobased Construction (in Dutch: Nationale Aanpak Biobased Bouwen). Such instruments are aimed at tackling hurdles and capitalizing opportunities across entire value chains (from sourcing of the biomass to the processing and use phases), and could similarly be initiated for the chemical sector as well. Therefore, specific attention should be directed in the policy sphere towards reducing consumption. A relatively new team at the Dutch ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, called Circulair Doen (in English: Acting Circular) seeks to address this gap and can be considered a good practice. It should be noted that, given the current Dutch political climate, limited public budgets are available to support biobased innovations, so bottom-up actions by e.g., supply chain actors and collaborative networks, are necessary to set the transition into motion.

In the construction sector, the implementation of quotas and targets related to both, biomass use and circularity, could begin with public and social construction projects. These projects can serve as examples for the private sector by demonstrating what is possible and by increasing the knowledge and skills of industry professionals. Starting with public procurement can also help avoid resistance from end users, such as homeowners, who might feel they are being forced into unfamiliar choices. It may also help prevent cost increases in the short term, as bio-based products are sometimes still less cost-effective and not as widely available as traditional materials.

The way sustainability criteria are implemented is also critical. They should promote the use of bio-based materials and support responsible forest management. Poorly designed criteria may fail to contribute to restoring forest health and resilience. Resource use taxes, for example those focused on virgin materials, also carry risks. If not designed carefully, they could unintentionally target renewable biomass sources, such as harvested wood. These policy instruments should be clearly directed at non-renewable materials only, in order to support the development of a more circular and bio-based construction sector.

3.4 Slovakia

The national DEPLOY workshop in Slovakia was organised by PEDAL Consulting on 18 June 2025. The event gathered 30 participants from across relevant stakeholder groups, including policy makers (7), industry representatives (4), researchers and academia (12), associations and clusters (3), and NGOs and civil society organisations (4). It provided the structure to discuss challenges and opportunities for advancing circular and bio-based solutions within the textile and construction sectors in the country.

3.4.1 Overview of analysed sectors

Textile sector

The textile sector in Slovakia is currently experiencing a gradual decline in manufacturing capacities and know-how, while at the same time facing growing pressures from global fast fashion imports and rising volumes of post-consumer textile waste. Despite these challenges, there is a growing momentum for circular and bio-based transformation, led primarily by grassroots initiatives, social enterprises, and emerging private actors. Platforms such as CYRKL and circular social enterprises have demonstrated concrete pathways for extending textile lifecycles through reuse, repair, and upcycling. However, this transformation remains fragmented and relatively under-supported. Slovakia currently does not have a dedicated national strategy for textile waste management, and an Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) scheme for textiles has not yet been introduced, unlike in some EU member states. Municipalities are increasingly challenged by the growing flow of used textiles, which are not yet integrated into the standard separated waste system. Stakeholders at the DEPLOY workshop described how local authorities are often left alone, managing textile collection and reuse in a regulatory vacuum.

A significant point of tension lies between low-cost, low-quality textile imports and the ambition to foster local, sustainable textile production. There is limited policy support for local fibre economies (e.g. hemp or regenerative cotton production), and insufficient incentives to promote longer textile lifecycles or domestic innovation. Educational and awareness activities exist (mainly among NGOs and eco-designers), but they are not yet systematically embedded in regional development or circular economy planning.

Nationally, Slovakia aligns with EU circularity goals in principle, yet policy translation into textile-specific instruments remains limited or under development. There is a strong need to define textile circularity as a strategic priority within national and regional waste plans and link it to industrial transformation opportunities. Without this, textile reuse and recycling are likely to remain marginal, and the burden will continue falling on local actors with limited support. Stakeholders call for functional public-private collaboration, financial instruments (e.g. VAT relief for reused materials), and strategic partnerships to scale up initiatives already delivering measurable environmental and social value.

Construction sector

The construction sector in Slovakia still operates predominantly under linear principles, with circular approaches emerging mainly in pilot projects or being referenced in urban planning discussions. The prevailing model tends to prioritize immediate cost considerations over lifecycle quality. Public procurement procedures often emphasize the lowest bid, which may indirectly favour conventional materials over reusable or bio-based alternatives.

Nonetheless, there are emerging positive signals. Pilot activities in demolition material reuse, design for disassembly, and the use of wood or hemp-based construction materials have started to appear, particularly in regions with active environmental NGOs or universities, however, their diffusion remains extremely limited. One of the main barriers is the lack of clear regulatory support and no requirement for selective demolition, except in voluntary or donor-funded projects. In many cases, potentially reusable construction materials are disposed of in landfills or downcycled, often without adequate tracking or certification systems in place.

Stakeholders at the DEPLOY conference emphasized that Slovakia's natural resources, such as forest biomass and marginal land suitable for bio-based crops, have not yet been systematically leveraged in the construction sector. The problem is systemic: wood from sustainable forestry is often exported as raw material, while low-grade imported materials dominate the local market. The economic model does not reward ecological construction (neither in public tendering nor in real estate valuation).

A key tension also exists in the limited capacity and knowledge at the municipal level to plan, manage, and enforce circular practices in buildings. Participants called for the creation of regional hubs to coordinate demolition, material reuse, and upskilling of local workers in eco-construction. Such hubs could act as knowledge brokers and facilitators between public authorities, private sector actors, and vocational institutions. Nationally, while Slovakia aligns with EU climate goals and sustainable construction narratives, concrete policy incentives for circular construction remain limited and are not yet effectively implemented. Stakeholders call for reforms in public procurement (introducing lifecycle criteria), green fiscal policies (e.g. tax incentives for reused materials), and state-led pilot investments in circular buildings, particularly in social housing and public infrastructure.

3.4.2 Strengths and weaknesses of policy instruments identified by stakeholders

The analysis of strengths and weaknesses of both direct regulation and market-based instruments in the textile and construction sector reveals key insights into how Slovakia can advance toward a

circular and bio-based economy. Stakeholder feedback during the DEPLOY workshop highlighted which instruments are most feasible, where systemic gaps persist, and what conditions must be in place to ensure effective implementation. It is worthy to mention that stakeholders also proposed additional policy instruments during the workshop and these have been included within this report and analysis. These findings help identify not only necessary policy adjustments, but also the readiness and needs of the textile industry to respond to this transition.

Hereafter the identified strengths, weaknesses and additional recommendations of stakeholders to the proposed policy instruments are summarized per sector.

Textile sector

Textile Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders identified *mandatory eco-design criteria* for bio-based textiles as a strong driver for encouraging the use of durable and renewable fibres, such as hemp and cotton. They emphasised its potential to improve product longevity and reduce environmental impact. However, they also noted higher production costs and the low market availability of quality bio-based fibres as significant barriers. It was suggested that social enterprises be included within emerging Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) systems, although this has not yet been implemented in Slovakia.

A new proposed instrument is to apply the *EPR scheme for textile producers*. This was seen as a means to internalise environmental costs and improve traceability of textile flows. However, participants pointed out that its implementation would require new institutional mechanisms, with compliance potentially challenging for SMEs.

Similarly, the suggested *ban on destruction of unsold goods* (related to landfilling and incineration of post-consumer textiles) was welcomed for preventing loss of reusable biomass-based material and aligning with the waste hierarchy, as well as promoting second-hand channels. Nonetheless, the lack of infrastructure for sorting and reuse – particularly among unprepared municipalities – was flagged as a major limitation. Likewise, participants considered that the enforcement of such a ban could be difficult, particularly for online retailers and importers. Stakeholders recommended that such measures be supported by R&D&I investments and awareness programmes for designers and SMEs. Finally, the *public procurement criteria* for bio-based textile products was considered as beneficial for a stable demand and visibility for sustainable materials. However, it faces difficulties in application due to the lack of circularity scoring in public procurement and limits set by lowest price.

For circularity, the aspects related to a mandatory minimum durability and reparability standards under the ecodesign criteria were viewed positively for their potential to extend product lifespans and reduce resource use. The complexity of monitoring compliance across imported goods, however, was considered a key challenge, with suggestions for national coordination and linkages to social enterprises for processing. Lastly, an additional measure suggested under direct regulation is the *legal obligation for municipalities to collect post-consumer textiles*. It was supported for improving recovery rates, though participants noted that municipalities currently lack the logistics and budget capacity to implement such a requirement.

Textile Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Participants supported the idea of *innovation subsidy for the development of new technologies and processes for bio-based textiles*, in particular directed as subsidies for regional hemp and linen cultivation as a way to stimulate domestic biomass inputs for circular textile chains. Still,

farmers' possible lack of interest or knowledge was recognised as a barrier, highlighting the need for methodological support and integration of these goals into procurement training.

The suggested *environmental tax* was discussed in particular with regards to penalties or fees on low-quality textile imports considered as a way to extend product lifespans and discourage fast fashion, but which could conflict with EU trade law, therefore reframing it as an extended responsibility surcharge was proposed.

The proposed *green VAT* (discussed also as *zero VAT*) on reused, recycled and bio-based textiles was seen as promoting circular economy objectives while supporting local fibre producers, though it could reduce tax revenue. Alignment with CAP measures and regional innovation platforms was suggested to mitigate these concerns. With regard to other circularity-focused market instruments, stakeholders assessed the *innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse and market penetration of innovative products* with special interest in supportive financial incentive for upcycling businesses as supportive for job creation, but vulnerable to over-reliance on grants and facing scaling challenges. Technical assistance, preferably managed at the regional level, was recommended. Finally, while a carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks was proposed, stakeholders shifted the discussion on the use of tax credits for circular business models. These were welcomed for rewarding innovation in repair, rental, and redesign, though SMEs' limited administrative knowledge might impede uptake.

Construction sector

Construction Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

The suggestion of a *quota for use of biobased materials in new buildings* was discussed in relation to setting a minimum bio-based content requirements in new public buildings. This was seen as capable of stimulating demand for wood and hemp-based materials, though concerns around supply chain readiness and cost impacts were noted. Stakeholders suggested embedding such requirements in local building codes, paired with incentives. *Mandatory maintenance protocols* for wooden buildings was another suggested measure, and identified as a means to increase longevity and value of bio-based structures, but could be perceived as an administrative burden by owners. Although the connection was not made by the stakeholders, this is in synergy with the proposed subsidy for refurbishment of buildings. However, this was not discussed in the workshop. In relation to sustainability aspects, instead of specific criteria for the eligibility of a quota, participants suggested a *ban on unsustainable biomass use* in construction. This was valued for its potential to reduce embodied carbon and biodiversity loss, but would require robust monitoring and verification mechanisms.

For circularity, the use of minimum reuse quotas in public tenders were suggested and considered an effective driver for secondary materials markets, but their success depends on the availability of certified reused components. *Ecodesign criteria* was considered in relation to design-for-disassembly obligations in public building codes. The measure was praised for lowering demolition waste but expected to be expensive for conventional developers. Under the suggested *demolition standards a mandatory selective demolition* for buildings over 400 m² could enable greater reuse and recycling of valuable materials, though this would be resource-intensive to monitor and document. Stakeholders proposed a phased introduction, beginning with pilot cities.

Construction Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Carbon credits for long-term storage in wooden buildings were seen to support the climate value of bio-based materials, but verifying and monitoring carbon flows presents a challenge. Therefore strong governance and collaboration would be required. A carbon tax on GHG emissions was not discussed with the participants, since the discussion shifted towards tax reductions for certified wood and hemp construction materials, which could improve competitiveness, though certification processes may be inaccessible for SMEs. Similarly, the *innovation subsidy to support the development of innovative bio-based construction materials*, derived in a discussion about public funding for regional bio-based construction hubs. In this case, that financial support could build local capacity and stimulate circular supply chains.

Under circularity, stakeholders identified the importance of providing financial support for digital material passports as enhancing traceability and reuse potential under the innovation subsidy. Although, it is considered that its adoption among SMEs might be low. The idea of a bonus scoring in tenders for circular building components came also as a suggestion under the innovation subsidy and could reward innovation without distorting competition. It will require methodological clarity and verification schemes would be necessary. Finally, the utilisation of a *material tax* to reduce virgin raw materials utilisation was not discussed. In its place a suggestion of a tax exemption or reduced VAT for reused materials was seen as a way to lower cost barriers for circular construction, though risks of fraud or quality issues with reused goods were acknowledged.

3.4.3 Prioritisation and implications for policy

During the voting exercise, stakeholders in Slovakia identified the following policy instruments as the most urgent for advancing circular and bio-based transitions in the textile and construction sectors:

Table 4: Prioritisation of policy instruments in Slovakia for the bio-based transition in the textile and construction sectors

Table 4. Prioritisation of policy instruments in Slovakia for the bio-based transition in the textile and construction sectors

Textile sector	Construction sector
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Legal obligation to collect post-consumer textiles at municipal level/ Mandatory separate textile collection (<i>suggested by stakeholders</i>) (8 votes) <i>Considered to apply in: Circularity/ Direct regulation</i> 2. Public procurement criteria for bio-based textile products - Green public procurement (5 votes) <i>Biomass/Direct regulation</i> 3. Green VAT for reused/recycled textiles (5 votes) <i>Circularity/Market-based instrument</i> 4. Environmental-tax on low quality textile materials (imports) (5 votes) <i>Biomass/Market-based instrument</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Demolition standards (9 votes) <i>Circularity/ Direct regulation</i> 2. Ecodesign criteria - Circularity criteria in public tenders (6 votes) <i>Circularity/ Direct regulation</i> 3. Quotas for bio-based materials (5 votes) <i>Biomass/Direct regulation</i> 4. Innovation subsidy - circular tech/materials (3 votes) <i>Circularity/Market-based instrument</i> 5. Innovation subsidy (bio-based materials) (2 votes) <i>Biomass/Market-based instrument</i>

<p>5. Ban on destruction of unsold clothing (4 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation</p> <p>6. Eco-design criteria for mandatory durability, reparability and recyclability standards (4 votes) Circularity/Direct regulation</p> <p>7. Innovation subsidy (bio-based textiles) for developing new technologies and practices (2 votes) Biomass/ Market-based instrument</p>	<p>6. Tax exemption or reduced VAT for reused materials (2 votes) Circularity/Market-based instrument</p> <p>7. <i>Ban on unsustainable biomass use</i> in construction(1 vote) Biomass/Direct regulation</p> <p>8. Carbon crediting (1 vote) Biomass/Market-based instrument</p>
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Participants highlighted **mandatory selective demolition** and **circular public procurement** as urgent priorities due to their direct impact on material reuse and market transformation. Financial incentives and innovation subsidies were seen as necessary to encourage adoption of sustainable materials. While digital material passports have potential, concerns remain about their current low uptake and complexity. Some measures, like carbon taxes, were viewed as important but politically challenging. Overall, a balanced combination of regulations, incentives, and pilot projects was recommended to ensure effective implementation.

Principally the municipal representatives in both sectors strongly backed the mandatory measures. For textiles, the introduction of separate textile collection was considered crucial to prevent textiles from mixing with general waste and to reduce environmental burdens, provided national coordination and funding are in place. In construction, municipal and regional representatives strongly supported mandatory selective demolition standards, seeing them as crucial for unlocking reuse potential and reducing landfill use. Their support was based on the practical need to improve demolition practices and material recovery at the local level.

On the other hand, SMEs and business representatives in textiles expressed concerns about the administrative burden of Extended Producer Responsibility schemes, especially for smaller importers and producers, and advocated for simplified procedures, phased implementation, and technical guidance. In construction, stakeholders raised concerns about the material tax and carbon credits, questioning their immediate feasibility and the potential to increase project costs without visible short-term benefits. This tension reflected a general caution towards financial instruments that might affect construction budgets without sufficient support or clarity.

Experts in waste management and circular economy supported the principle of banning the destruction of unsold textile goods, yet emphasized the importance of enforcement mechanisms and alternative pathways such as reuse networks or donation obligations, while noting monitoring challenges—especially for e-commerce platforms and imported goods. Overall, support in both sectors was strongest for practical, regulation-based tools tied to collection, demolition, and procurement, while more abstract or complex market-based instruments (such as financial taxes and credits) received mixed reactions, especially where administrative burden or unclear economic return was perceived.

Across both sectors, stakeholders pointed to several existing barriers or missing enablers:

- At the systemic level, lack of coordination and fragmented governance is a hindering factor in both sectors. Slovakia’s textile sector is constrained by lack of EPR legislation, and unclear national-municipal roles. Its construction sector lacks coordination between ministries responsible for construction, environment, and procurement for the implementation of proposed policy instruments.

- Expected administrative burdens linked to compliance (e.g., under EPR systems) and complex regulatory and certification procedures.
- Insufficient infrastructure for collection, sorting, and certification of reused textiles and construction materials.
- High upfront costs for circular technologies, materials certification, and compliance audits.
- Supply chain readiness, especially for meeting bio-based content quotas in construction.
- Lack of training and technical assistance for SMEs, municipalities, and procurement officers. This will support the growing interest from municipalities in reuse practices.
- Lack of access to green finance, including targeted subsidies and low-interest loans.

The transition to a CBBE in both the textile and construction sectors in Slovakia calls for moderate to significant policy adjustments, with particular attention to clarifying the division of responsibilities between ministries and local authorities. For textiles, the absence of coordinated collection systems and sustainability criteria in procurement must be supported by funding, technical assistance, and legal harmonization. Adjustments should prioritize enabling local implementation while aligning with upcoming EU-level obligations. Active social enterprises, increasing public awareness, and existing experiences with separate waste collection reforms create a strong foundation for advancing circular textile policies. Improving coordination, funding mechanisms, and administrative capacity at the local level are necessary for their success.

In construction, there is a high need to align public procurement rules, building standards, and waste legislation to support circular construction practices. Low integration of circularity in procurement frameworks and the absence of legal obligations for material reuse constitute key barriers. To maximize impact and limit disruption, policy changes should be phased in, beginning with pilot regions or targeted public investments and reinforced by clear guidelines, technical tools, and explicit incentives, fostering public-private partnerships to build infrastructure and foster knowledge transfer. Coordination between ministries—specifically those responsible for construction, environment, and economy—is essential to break down regulatory silos and ensure efficient implementation.

3.5 Spain

In Spain, the DEPLOY policy reflection process was conducted via targeted surveys, managed by CIRCE (plastics sector) and TECNALIA (textile sector), and circulated to selected stakeholders from July 3 to August 17, 2025. For the textile survey, four respondents participated (including policy makers and representatives from associations or clusters); for plastics, five stakeholders responded (representing policy makers, industry, academia, and associations).

3.5.1 Overview of analysed sectors

Textile sector

In Spain, the shift toward a circular, bio-based textile economy is driven by regulatory pressures, market demand, and public-private collaboration. Key incentives include new European regulations on eco-design, product traceability, and waste management, as well as national initiatives promoting water reuse and sustainability. Market forces—such as growing consumer interest in sustainable products and the increasing role of informed purchasing decisions—further

encourage change. Public support through funding, tax incentives for R&D, and sustainable public procurement policies also play a critical role. Despite this momentum, the textile value chain faces challenges including limited technical and regulatory knowledge, difficulties replacing harmful chemicals, lack of coordination across related sectors, and a need for practical tools to implement sustainability. In response, actors of the sector have launched a range of projects aimed at developing circular business models, testing bio-based materials, and creating new waste recovery routes. These initiatives have fostered collaboration between industry and research, facilitated the exchange of knowledge, and helped prepare the ground for broader adoption by identifying viable solutions, sharing results with companies, and planning for future scale-up. The expected effect is a more resilient, innovative, and environmentally aligned textile sector.

In the context of policy design aimed at fostering circularity and bioeconomy in the textile sector, it is important to recognize the current structural and regulatory burdens faced by companies operating in Spain. Industry actors emphasize that existing environmental compliance requirements—particularly those related to REACH regulations, wastewater treatment, emissions control, chemical management, and waste handling—already impose substantial costs on businesses. In addition, companies are confronting social challenges, such as high levels of workforce absenteeism and difficulties in retaining qualified talent.

There is a perception that proposed regulatory and market-based instruments to support circular practices may not sufficiently reflect these operational realities. From the industry's perspective, effective policy instruments must be closely aligned with market dynamics and should first address the pressing need to ease or better support the costs of current regulatory compliance.

While the transition to circular models holds promise for reducing environmental impacts and associated costs over the long term, it is commented that this transition will only be viable if accompanied by instruments that also provide short-term relief or support for the existing burdens. Without such alignment, *companies may perceive sustainability initiatives as additional layers of complexity rather than pathways to operational efficiency.*

Plastics sector

In Spain, the plastics sector is advancing toward a more circular and bio-based model, influenced by EU strategies such as the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the European Plastics Strategy. This shift is visible through rising innovation in materials, growing recycling capacity, and increased substitution of fossil-based plastics by bio-based and recycled alternatives. The plastics industry represents approximately 5.5% of Spain's industrial GDP and plays a major role in employment and value creation. The country ranks among the top four in the EU for packaging recycling, with recycled volumes reaching 1.1 million tonnes in 2022. Bioplastics production is also gaining traction, with Europe accounting for over 60% of global output and Spain benefiting from participation in European platforms such as the Circular Plastics Alliance.

This transition is supported by a growing ecosystem of companies, technology centers, academic institutions, and clusters working together to improve ecodesign, mechanical and chemical recycling, and certification and traceability systems. The feedback received confirms widespread support for innovation subsidies, carbon pricing mechanisms, and SME-targeted support as drivers of change.

Stakeholders highlight the emergence of circular business models, including reuse schemes, local recycling hubs, sustainable public procurement initiatives, and digital traceability systems. However, the pace of this transformation remains constrained by structural and regulatory barriers.

Despite the positive momentum, several tensions persist. Stakeholders across industry, academia, and policy agree that national efforts often lag behind EU ambition, especially in relation to the lack of unified traceability and certification frameworks for recycled and bio-based plastics, insufficient fiscal alignment with circularity goals, and fragmented governance between national and regional levels. This lack of coherence is particularly problematic for SMEs, which struggle with the complexity of overlapping regulations and limited access to administrative and technical support.

Survey responses also raise concerns about premature or overly rigid regulatory instruments, such as caps on biomass use or unclear ecodesign obligations. These measures may unintentionally penalize emerging innovations or raise compliance burdens without delivering clear environmental benefits.

At the same time, there is strong support for enhancing green public procurement, which is still underused in Spain. Stakeholders recommend simplification of contracting procedures, the inclusion of clear sustainability criteria, and capacity-building for local administrations to make these policies effective and accessible. There is also broad interest in aligning fiscal instruments, such as carbon taxes and VAT reform, with sustainability objectives, provided that such measures are implemented progressively, transparently, and with attention to their socioeconomic impacts.

Ultimately, survey respondents stress the need for a comprehensive national roadmap for circularity in plastics. This roadmap should be backed by inter-ministerial coordination, long-term funding mechanisms, and meaningful engagement with industry, academia, and civil society. Such an approach is essential to ensure regulatory predictability, foster innovation, and enable the sector's alignment with EU goals while maintaining economic competitiveness.

3.5.2 Strengths and weaknesses of policy instruments identified by stakeholders

Textile sector

Textile Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Stakeholders recognized that a *quota for the use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock* in textile production and imports is effective and can genuinely increase demand for biological materials—so long as there is inspection and enforcement. This quota is seen as incentivizing innovation and the development of new bio-based products. However, it requires a mature and reliable supply chain and brings a risk of increased costs and potential misalignment with current industrial capabilities. Several noted this instrument should be preceded by studies to guarantee technical feasibility and avoid undermining price competitiveness.

Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content was acknowledged to set an example, especially if accompanied by publicity, as it generates stable demand and can facilitate economies of scale. However, stakeholders pointed out that public administrations represent an insignificant part of the market, and there may be technical and regulatory barriers to defining standardized “bio” criteria at national and European levels. Many SMEs and micro-enterprises often lack knowledge of, or fear, innovative public procurement processes.

Regarding *sustainability criteria for biomass* to be eligible for quotas or public procurement, stakeholders indicated clear alignment with the European Green Deal and credit this tool with

avoiding negative impacts on alternative uses of biomass. Still, there was concern that it may create regulatory burdens for SMEs if processes are not sufficiently simplified.

Ecodesign criteria were also highlighted for their great potential to improve product durability and recyclability, as they align with the EU Textile Strategy. Nevertheless, stakeholders believed these require consistent and well-structured policies that establish robust networks between the sector and innovation-promoting actors, as well as significant investment in redesign and training—especially for SMEs.

The *ban on destruction of unsold goods* was seen as highly effective in creating demand for secondary products, reducing waste, and promoting reuse or recycling channels. Stakeholders saw potential for new value chains and noted that SMEs could benefit from their greater flexibility and adaptability to small production batches. However, a minimum level of ecodesign is necessary to ensure surpluses are reusable and/or recyclable, and bans could impact logistics, inventory management, and increase production costs due to smaller batch manufacturing.

Finally, the introduction of a *quota for use of recycled material in textile production and imports* was regarded by stakeholders as an effective measure to encourage the use of post-consumer textile waste and to improve the sector's overall circularity. Respondents emphasized that, similar to biological material quotas, such a requirement can increase the uptake of recycled content provided that it is grounded in feasibility studies and market realities. Nonetheless, concerns were raised over limited availability and quality of post-consumer recycled material, as well as the nascent state of treatment technologies—particularly as mechanical recycling is often unsuitable for post-consumer textiles. Without prior studies to guarantee technical feasibility and competitiveness, stakeholders cautioned that this quota could unintentionally reduce the sector's competitiveness.

Textile Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Innovation subsidies for new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles gathered good acceptance and were seen as effective. Stakeholders observed that these subsidies promote applied research, development of sustainable products, accelerate technological transition, and encourage knowledge exchange between companies and research institutions. However, concerns were raised that if maintained too long, such subsidies can cause inefficiencies. Key recommendations emphasized the need for clear objectives, time-limited implementation, effective monitoring and evaluation, and adaptation to the SME landscape to avoid concentration among larger firms. Also, *innovation subsidies for innovative textile reuse* were also described as popular and effective when properly controlled. These incentives can drive the development of key technologies—such as sorting and chemical/mechanical recycling—and can stimulate the application of circular economy principles. However, stakeholders warned that their efficacy depends on coordination with collection and sorting systems, which remain underdeveloped in Spain, as well as on careful definition of subsidy program objectives and timeframes.

Environmental taxes were perceived as effective in internalizing environmental costs in product pricing and promoting sustainable alternatives. Still, stakeholders expressed that increased costs—especially from a lack of harmonized sustainability criteria—could lead to a loss in competitiveness, offshoring, and disproportionate effects on lower-income consumers and SMEs. The importance of fair implementation, strong criteria, and revenue recycling for sector support was noted.

The introduction of *green VAT* was described as effective and fair, especially for reuse, since reused products are otherwise taxed twice. Stakeholders found it attractive for both consumers

and businesses and noted its ability to promote recycled textiles without imposing new burdens. Yet its application may comparatively reduce public revenue, and it requires national-level tax modifications and European Commission approval.

A *carbon tax* was seen to provide economic incentive to reduce fossil-based raw materials, consistent with the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) and climate goals. However, the lack of clarity or consensus on the carbon footprint of synthetic versus natural materials makes this a complex instrument. It is also considered potentially burdensome for companies still reliant on fossil-based materials, particularly SMEs with lower adaptability.

Plastic sector

Plastic Sector – Direct Regulation Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Product subsidies for bioplastics were considered to stimulate demand and local production of bioplastics, boost agricultural and forestry sectors, and support new markets aligned with EU Green Deal targets. However, stakeholders warned of greenwashing risks if such support is not backed by strict sustainability criteria. They also pointed to possible tensions when biomass is diverted from food or energy uses and noted the risk of subsidy dependency. Price signals alone should not drive the market, or this could lead to declining quality, resource overuse, or environmental rebound effects.

Sustainability criteria for biomass sourcing are widely supported in principle and seen as aligned with EU taxonomy and environmental goals, promoting responsible sourcing and long-term sustainability. Nevertheless, the absence of clear national criteria in Spain, fragmented implementation, and potential administrative burdens—particularly for SMEs—were cited as critical weaknesses. Stakeholders recommended tailoring criteria to regional biomass realities and supporting implementation with technical guidance and simplified certification.

A *biomass use cap* or ceiling can prevent overexploitation of natural resources and help balance biomass uses across sectors, promoting efficiency. Nonetheless, stakeholders cautioned that reliable monitoring and traceability systems are needed for successful implementation, and setting rigid caps could unintentionally stifle innovation or penalize emerging bio-based technologies. The measure should be implemented cautiously, with a dynamic and transparent review mechanism, piloted sector-by-sector, and backed by robust data and safeguards.

Mandatory *recycled content quotas* in plastics were recognized for generating stable demand and driving investments in recycling infrastructure. Yet, stakeholders warned that the availability and quality of recyclate could become a bottleneck, especially for small producers who may struggle with compliance unless sufficient support mechanisms exist.

Ecodesign requirements for plastic products were valued for facilitating reuse and recyclability right from the design stage and for supporting innovation. However, they require industry to make short-term redesign investments, and SMEs in particular need training and technical support to adopt these measures.

Public procurement criteria for sustainable plastics can serve as a market driver for circular products and encourage innovation through demand pull, but implementation is limited by low institutional capacity, unclear criteria, and complex tender procedures, issues especially acute for small suppliers. Recommendations included capacity building for public buyers and adoption

of simplified, SME-friendly criteria, such as inclusion of mandatory percentages of recycled content and environmental impacts in scoring.

Finally, the *ban on single-use plastic products* was widely recognized for reducing waste streams, signalling strong policy commitment, and enjoying high public awareness. However, stakeholders noted potential resistance from some industry sectors and consumers, especially if viable alternatives are not available. Successful bans have been accompanied by immediate alternatives, clear definitions, enforcement, and transition assistance for affected industries.

Plastic Sector – Market-Based Instruments (Biomass & Circularity Factsheets)

Innovation subsidies for new bioplastics and circular solutions were credited with encouraging technological development, facilitating industry-academia collaboration, and energizing green startups and SMEs, particularly in recycling technologies and traceability. Risks noted included potential dependency if not complemented by structural measures, the need for robust R&D strategies, monitoring to avoid low-impact solutions, and ensuring subsidies are strongly SME-oriented. Suggestions included prioritizing projects with clear traceability, compostability, and market potential, and adapting schemes to SME needs through tools such as vouchers and simplified access.

A *carbon tax on emissions* on low-value biomass uses, internalizes environmental costs and discourages inefficient or unsustainable practices. Still, stakeholders flagged the challenge of clear definitions, warned against disproportionate impacts on SMEs or rural actors (unless phased in or compensated), and recommended that revenues be dedicated to innovation, rural support, or traceability platforms. Gradual rollout and ongoing stakeholder dialogue were considered essential for acceptability.

A *carbon tax on fossil-based plastics* was regarded as a measure to encourage substitution of fossil materials and make circular alternatives more competitive. Yet, concerns were raised about additional costs for consumers, especially if the tax is not implemented at the EU level and costs are merely passed along, reducing competitiveness and public acceptance. Stakeholders stressed the need for revenue recycling and care to avoid negative social impacts.

3.5.3 Prioritisation and implications for policy

In addition to the previous classifications and identification of strengths and weaknesses, survey takers were invited to evaluate two groups of policy instruments (“Policy Sets”) corresponding to the policy factsheets developed within the framework of the SUSTRACK project. Survey participants were asked to indicate which of the policy sets they considered most suitable for the Spanish context in each of the analysed sectors.

Textile sector

To limit the extensive use of raw biomass in the textile sector, survey takers expressed a preference for elements from both Policy Set 1a: direct regulation and Policy Set 1b: market-based instruments, suggesting a combined approach may be most effective. Specifically, several respondents favoured the inclusion of **quotas and sustainability criteria for biomass** from Set 1a, recognizing their potential to establish clear targets and ensure responsible sourcing practices.

However, there was also a strong endorsement of **market-based instruments** from Policy Set 1b. These were valued for their **flexibility and capacity to incentivize innovation** without imposing rigid constraints. Regional textile industry representatives, such as ATEVAL, highlighted that **innovation subsidies** enable the adaptation of new technologies to the specific capabilities and conditions of the Spanish textile sector.

Additionally, **well-designed environmental taxes** were seen as effective tools to correct market failures and drive behavioural change, provided they avoid creating excessive regulatory burdens. Overall, respondents emphasized that **efficient, innovation-friendly fiscal mechanisms** are key to facilitating a sustainable transition while maintaining the sector's competitiveness.

Regarding the most suitable set of policies to promote circularity in the textile sector, survey takers' responses reflect a balanced and pragmatic perspective, with a general preference for market-based instruments (Policy Set 2b) while acknowledging the importance of certain regulatory measures from Policy Set 2a. Specifically, some participants favoured a combination of **ecodesign quotas and criteria** from Set 2a alongside **green VAT incentives** from Set 2b, highlighting the value of integrating both regulatory and economic tools.

Policy Set 2b received strong support for its ability to encourage circular practices through economic incentives directed at both consumption and investment. Instruments such as **differentiated VAT for circular products** and **direct subsidies for recycling** were viewed as especially suitable for SMEs, offering a more accessible and less burdensome path to sustainability. These tools were also noted for their potential to stimulate local circular economy collaborations.

Conversely, while regulatory instruments under Set 2a (e.g., mandatory ecodesign requirements) were seen as important, several respondents emphasized the need for their gradual implementation, accompanied by technical assistance and financial support. This approach is considered essential to ensure widespread adoption and minimize potential disruptions, particularly among smaller enterprises.

As a final item in the survey, based on their perspective and experience, respondents were asked to explain shortly what policy proposal could help accelerate the circular and bio-based transition in the textile sector in Spain, thus, eventually addressing instruments and actions that have not been mentioned above.

Finally, stakeholders provided a range of concrete proposals and considerations aimed at advancing the circular and bio-based transformation of the Spanish textile industry. Their contributions can be grouped into several key areas:

1. Need for Global Context and Trade Considerations

Stakeholders warned that environmental policies, if not assessed in a global context, could increase production costs and thus reduce the price competitiveness of European companies. They emphasized that without accompanying international trade policy measures (such as tariffs), such policies could unintentionally benefit unsustainable foreign production and lead to the decline of the European textile sector—the opposite of the intended goal.

2. European and National Support Programs

Several participants stressed the importance of continuing to promote **European calls** focused on the **circular and bio-based transition** specifically for the textile sector. They advocated for:

- **Mixed financial instruments** funded through public and EU sources

- Complementary **national and regional support lines**

Key areas to be supported include:

- **R&D for recycled and bio-based fibers**
- **Digitalization in ecodesign**
- **Creation of local hubs** for textile collection, sorting, and recycling

Expected impact: **faster technological and regulatory adaptation**, increased **competitiveness**, and improved **environmental and circularity indicators**.

3. Measures Adapted to the SME Landscape

Given that most textile companies in Spain are SMEs, the following additional recommendations were proposed:

- Establishment of **micro-financing lines** combining grants and soft loans
- Promotion of **SME consortia** to share recycling infrastructure, logistics platforms, or innovation centres
- **Priority access for SMEs** in sustainable public procurement programs, with criteria adapted to their capabilities
- Development of **specific training programs** on circularity and bioeconomy for both technical and managerial staff

4. Suggested Key Actors for Implementation

Stakeholders identified several relevant actors for implementing these measures:

- **Ministry of Industry**
- **Ministry for Ecological Transition**
- **Regional governments**
- **CDTI (Center for the Development of Industrial Technology)**
- **Technology institutes** (e.g., AITEX)
- **Sectoral associations** (e.g., ATEVAL, TEXFOR)

Plastic sector

Regarding a sustainable use of biomass, survey responses on biomass policies reflected a diversity of positions, with no absolute consensus between Policy Set 1a (direct regulation) and Policy Set 1b (market-based instruments).

Stakeholders from academia and the policy sector favoured Policy Set 1a, arguing that mandatory sustainability criteria and legal limits (caps) are essential to avoid negative environmental impacts and to ensure the responsible use of biomass resources. For them, product subsidies under Set 1a are justifiable only when coupled with strong sustainability safeguards. They also expressed concern over greenwashing risks in the absence of regulation.

On the other hand, industry and cluster representatives leaned toward Policy Set 1b, highlighting the value of innovation subsidies and carbon taxes to stimulate market transformation without the rigidity of regulatory mandates. These actors viewed fiscal tools as more flexible and innovation-friendly, especially during early deployment phases of bio-based plastics.

Despite this divergence, all profiles acknowledged the need for coordination between both approaches. A recurring proposal was to **combine targeted subsidies and carbon pricing (Set 1b) with clear, enforceable sustainability criteria (Set 1a) applied gradually**. This hybrid approach was seen as particularly important to support SMEs, prevent biomass overexploitation, and create a predictable investment environment.

There was also agreement on the lack of national sustainability criteria, the need for harmonized certification systems, and the importance of traceability mechanisms. Without these, both sets of policies risk limited effectiveness.

In short, while preferences diverged between direct regulation and economic instruments, stakeholders generally supported a balanced mix, adapted to the maturity of the bio-based plastics sector and implemented in phases.

On the other hand, to support circularity in the plastic sector survey takers expressed strong overall support for Policy Set 2a (direct regulation) as the most effective tool to accelerate circularity in the plastics sector. **Mandatory recycled content quotas, product ecodesign requirements, and bans on problematic items** such as single-use plastics were considered essential to drive immediate and systemic change across the value chain.

However, many stakeholders also acknowledged the complementary value of selected market-based instruments from Policy Set 2b, particularly **innovation subsidies and green public procurement incentives**. These tools were viewed as necessary to reduce financial and technical barriers, especially for SME's, and to foster collaborative innovation ecosystems.

Industry respondents warned that regulatory measures must be introduced progressively, with clear guidance and realistic timelines. There is a shared concern that rigid obligations without support mechanisms could slow innovation or exclude smaller players from compliance. As such, a hybrid approach combining Set 2a mandates with Set 2b incentives was suggested by multiple actors, particularly for enabling reuse systems, chemical recycling, and digital traceability.

Policy Set 2b alone was seen as insufficient to generate structural change, as it relies on voluntary uptake and may lack the force to redirect entire markets. Conversely, Policy Set 2a was perceived as the main driver for market transformation, provided that it is accompanied by adequate public support, procurement reform, and technical capacity-building.

Based on stakeholder feedback, the following recommendations are proposed to foster the transition toward circular and bio-based plastics in Spain:

1. **Establish a national roadmap for circular and bio-based plastics**, aligned with EU directives but tailored to Spain's industrial and territorial realities. This roadmap should clarify long-term goals, policy instruments, and transition milestones.
2. **Introduce mandatory recycled content quotas and ecodesign requirements**, with sector-specific thresholds and implementation calendars. These measures should be backed by technical support for SMEs.
3. **Develop national sustainability criteria for biomass sourcing**, harmonized with EU taxonomy and verified through streamlined certification schemes. This should include traceability requirements and social safeguards.

4. **Reform and simplify green public procurement**, ensuring that tenders explicitly reward circular and bio-based materials. Capacity building is needed at the local level to support implementation.
5. **Support SME's and innovation ecosystems** through targeted subsidies for pilot projects, reuse systems, and traceability platforms. Innovation vouchers and simplified application processes were specifically requested.
6. **Introduce carbon pricing mechanisms** (e.g., taxes on fossil-based plastics or low-value biomass uses), but implement them gradually and transparently, with revenues recycled into circular economy support funds.
7. **Invest in monitoring and traceability infrastructure**, including digital platforms to certify recycled and bio-based content. Stakeholders stressed the need for reliable data to enforce regulations and build trust.
8. **Foster coordination across government levels**, avoiding regulatory fragmentation and aligning regional and national strategies.

4 CAPACITY BUILDING

The session combined **presentations, concrete examples, and an interactive Q&A session**, ensuring that stakeholders could:

- Gain an **overview of the available tools** and their potential applications;
- Understand **how these tools could be directly used** or accessed through SUSTRACK's expertise;
- Explore **practical examples** of how the tools can inform decision-making and support the deployment of circular bio-based strategies;
- **Ask questions and clarify specific doubts or curiosities**, fostering an open dialogue with the presenters.

A key strength of the session was a brief **practical demonstration** offered alongside the theoretical overview. Where possible, each tool was briefly showcased in action, allowing participants to see its functionality and potential applications in real-world scenarios. This combined approach helped **raise awareness and spark interest**, providing stakeholders with a **first exposure** to the tools and their **value propositions for research, policymaking, and industry planning**.

Building on the DEPLOY experience, SUSTRACK will develop a comprehensive toolkit that will integrate a **written component**, summarising all key information related to the tools presented, with a **video component**, replicating the presentations delivered during DEPLOY. This combined format will enable **broader dissemination and easier accessibility**, allowing stakeholders to revisit the material at their own pace.

The toolkit will not only be **distributed and showcased during upcoming SUSTRACK events**, such as the final conference, but will also be **shared through the project's communication channels** (website and social media) to maximise outreach and impact. In addition, opportunities for further

capacity-building sessions and tailored analyses will remain available upon stakeholder request, ensuring that policymakers, industry actors, and researchers are equipped with **practical instruments** to guide the transition towards a sustainable circular bio-based economy.

Looking ahead, the **SUSTRACK monitoring system** has strong potential for future exploitation. Thanks to its intuitive design and visual interface, it can serve as an accessible entry point for stimulating discussion within panels and working groups, particularly in countries taking their first steps toward developing a bioeconomy strategy or roadmap. In this sense, it can provide valuable support to those countries that do not yet have a dedicated monitoring system, helping them build initial capacities. Moreover, we expect that some of the SUSTRACK functionalities could serve as inspiration for the further development of the **EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (EU-BMS)**. As the EU-BMS represents the central reference for monitoring the bioeconomy at European level, integrating features such as **benchmarking analyses** or **visual linkages between bioeconomy indicators and the SDGs** could significantly enhance its relevance, usability, and overall effectiveness.

Building on GEM's open-source design, future utilization of the tool can focus on expanding to additional EU countries, refining biomass pathways and additional sectoral interactions, and integrating broader environmental and socio-economic externalities. Complementing these capabilities with interfaces to land-use, energy system, or spatial planning models could further enhance the analysis of resource allocation, infrastructure needs, and investment strategies. Such extensions would allow researchers and policymakers to explore ambitious biomass transition scenarios with greater granularity, capture cross-sectoral trade-offs, and provide actionable insights for designing sustainable and integrated EU biomass policies.

Lessons learned from the capacity building

A key lesson from the development of the SUSTRACK monitoring system and its demonstration is the importance of creating tools that are accessible to a non-expert audience. User-friendly interfaces and clear visualizations play a central role in making complex data and indicators understandable beyond the scientific community. Such accessibility is crucial for facilitating the uptake of scientific evidence by a wider audience, including policymakers, stakeholders, and practitioners, thereby strengthening the link between knowledge generation and decision-making.

The capacity building sessions demonstrated that systems thinking and system dynamics are inherently complex, and a 45-minute session is insufficient to fully explore the concepts, particularly given the scope of the GEM model. Participants were able to grasp the high-level principles and workflow, but fully understanding model structure, feedback loops, and scenario implications requires longer, more interactive engagement. This challenge of balancing depth of results with clarity of communication has also been highlighted by other EU Horizon projects during bilateral conferences, underscoring that concise sessions facilitate engagement but limit participants' ability to critically interact with detailed model outputs. Future capacity building efforts should consider extended or modular sessions to better align comprehension with practical application.

Conferences raise awareness but don't build real capability. In Slovak conditions, systems thinking (CLD) and GEM need modular, interactive sessions with domestic case work and side-by-side use of the monitoring dashboards (spider charts, sector comparisons) to anchor scenarios in local data. To achieve better results, a longer-term engagement with stakeholders would be needed, allowing for thematic continuity and creating space for deeper understanding of the methods as well as

stronger outcomes. In practice, pair targeted regulation with enabling finance, green procurement, and implementation support, and keep all tools accessible to non-experts with clear visuals and plain-language narratives to keep discussion evidence-driven and decision-oriented.

5 CROSS-CUTTING INSIGHTS AND LESSONS LEARNED

The DEPLOY Conferences and survey results across Germany, Italy, Netherlands-Belgium, Slovakia, and Spain generated a rich set of stakeholder reflections on the feasibility, strengths, and barriers of policy instruments for advancing the circular bio-based transition. By reflecting on the stakeholder feedback and analysis of proposed policy instruments in each country cross-cutting insights are highlighted in this concluding chapter. By looking at similar sectors across different countries, as well as drawing out cross-sectoral patterns, several insights and lessons emerge that are directly relevant for both national and EU-level policy development.

5.1 Converging insights across sectors and countries

5.1.1 Standards and quotas as central drivers

A clear convergence across all countries is the strong support for regulatory instruments such as recycled or bio-based content quotas and ecodesign standards. In the plastics sector, recycled content requirements were consistently highlighted as both impactful and feasible when combined with adequate monitoring. Similarly, in textiles, ecodesign requirements were seen as essential to address product longevity, reparability, and recyclability. In chemicals, stakeholders from Germany and Netherlands-Belgium emphasized the importance of feedstock diversification quotas and sustainability criteria for biomass inputs.

Stakeholders see these instruments as providing long-term certainty for investment, creating level playing fields across companies, and stimulating innovation. The common message is that without binding standards or quotas, market signals alone will not suffice to shift production and consumption patterns.

5.1.2 Limited enthusiasm for taxation and pricing mechanisms

By contrast, market-based instruments of a fiscal nature (e.g. taxes on virgin materials, carbon pricing, resource levies) received little support across almost all contexts. The reasons were strikingly consistent: risks to competitiveness in global markets, potential negative effects on SMEs, concerns about administrative complexity, and low public acceptance. Even in countries with relatively advanced circular economy agendas, such as Belgium and Netherlands, stakeholders acknowledged the theoretical merit of taxation but doubted its practical feasibility without strong EU-wide coordination.

The exception is subsidies and targeted financial incentives, which were welcomed across all countries. Stakeholders valued subsidies for innovation, recycling infrastructure, refurbishment, and SME adaptation as necessary enablers, particularly during transition phases.

5.1.3 Enforcement and administrative capacity as critical bottlenecks

A recurring concern across all countries is the difficulty of enforcing ambitious regulations. Stakeholders warned that quotas or bans lose effectiveness if not supported by robust monitoring,

clear reporting obligations, and sufficient administrative capacity. This was especially evident in Slovakia and Spain, where limited institutional resources were noted as barriers. In larger industrial economies like Germany and Italy, enforcement challenges were linked to the complexity of tracking compliance across highly diversified value chains.

5.1.4 Acceptance and political sensitivity

Stakeholders repeatedly stressed that even well-designed instruments risk resistance if public or political acceptance is not secured. For example, bans on single-use plastics are widely recognized as impactful, yet in some countries industry stakeholders warned about backlash from consumers and SMEs. In textiles, proposals to restrict fast-fashion practices sparked debate about consumer behaviour and international trade implications. Acceptance emerged as a decisive factor shaping the speed and depth of implementation.

5.2 Sector-specific insights from cross-country results

5.2.1 Construction sector (Slovakia; Netherlands-Belgium)

Construction stakeholders converged on the importance of standards for reused and bio-based materials, material passports, and quotas for recycled inputs. Both countries emphasized refurbishment incentives as a cost-effective way to reduce emissions and resource use. However, Slovakia highlighted affordability challenges for SMEs and consumers, while in Netherlands-Belgium the debate centred on aligning national standards with EU frameworks to avoid fragmentation.

Standards vs. Affordability

Netherlands-Belgium: Stakeholders supported material passports and standards for reused and bio-based materials, reflecting a mature debate on circular construction and well-developed demonstration projects.

Slovakia: By contrast, Slovak stakeholders highlighted affordability concerns. SMEs and associations warned that strict standards or quotas could increase costs for builders and consumers, making subsidies and phased introduction essential.

This shows the contrast between regulatory maturity and innovation ecosystems in north-western Europe and economic constraints in smaller markets like Slovakia.

5.2.2 Chemical sector (Germany; Netherlands-Belgium)

For the chemical sector, stakeholders consistently prioritized feedstock diversification and sustainability criteria for biomass. German stakeholders emphasized the urgency of reducing dependence on fossil-based inputs, while also pointing to competitiveness concerns if such quotas are introduced without international alignment. Belgian-Dutch stakeholders, by contrast, stressed the need for innovation subsidies to develop safer, less toxic alternatives. Across both contexts, there was scepticism about the feasibility of carbon pricing for chemicals given the global nature of the industry.

Competing priorities between feedstock diversification and innovation

Germany: Stakeholders focused on quotas for non-fossil feedstocks as the central lever to drive systemic change. Concerns centre on competitiveness in export markets and the risk of carbon leakage if measures are not internationally coordinated.

Netherlands-Belgium: While also supportive of sustainability criteria, stakeholders placed stronger emphasis on subsidies for innovation, particularly to accelerate the development of safer, less toxic alternatives. Their position reflects the stronger presence of R&D-intensive chemical clusters and a policy culture oriented toward innovation incentives.

The divergence illustrates how industrial structure shapes priorities. On one side, in Germany stakeholders prioritized systemic feedstock shifts, while feedback from Netherlands-Belgium experts emphasizes technological upgrading through innovation subsidies.

5.2.3 Textiles sector (Italy; Slovakia; Spain)

Textile discussions highlighted ecodesign requirements as the most powerful lever. Italy and Slovakia emphasized reparability and durability standards, while Spain (through survey input) confirmed strong support for ecodesign but also noted enforcement difficulties given the fragmented SME-dominated sector. Bans on destruction of unsold goods gained traction in Italy, whereas in Slovakia, subsidies for recycling and refurbishment were considered more feasible in the short term. Divergence arose around fiscal instruments, with some stakeholders supporting penalties for fast-fashion products, while others warned of risks to competitiveness against imports.

Fast Fashion vs. Durability Standards

Italy: Stakeholders strongly supported bans on the destruction of unsold goods and mandatory durability and reparability standards. However, textile SMEs stressed that compliance could increase production costs, raising concerns about competitiveness against imports from non-EU producers.

Slovakia: SMEs in Slovakia echoed concerns about costs but placed more emphasis on financial support for recycling and refurbishment, reflecting their limited innovation capacity and lower margins.

Spain: Survey feedback showed alignment with ecodesign priorities but highlighted limited national enforcement capacity as a barrier to ensuring compliance.

In this case the same instrument (ecodesign standards) is perceived differently. In Italy as an industrial discipline tool, in Slovakia as an aspirational but costly measure, and in Spain as desirable but administratively challenging.

5.2.4 Plastics (Germany; Italy; Spain)

In plastics, recycled content quotas were the dominant priority across all three countries. Stakeholders recognized these quotas as directly pushing markets toward secondary raw material

use. However, concerns about insufficient recycling infrastructure were repeatedly raised, especially in Spain and Italy. German stakeholders further emphasized alignment with EU Single-Use Plastics Directive and international standards. Subsidies for R&D into advanced recycling were widely welcomed, while taxation of virgin plastic was viewed as risky unless implemented at EU scale.

Recycling Infrastructure Gaps

Germany: Stakeholders expressed confidence in implementing recycled content quotas, backed by existing infrastructure and alignment with EU Single-Use Plastics legislation.

Italy: While supportive of quotas, stakeholders raised concerns about insufficient recycling infrastructure, particularly in southern regions, and the risk of raising production costs without parallel investment in waste management systems.

Spain: Survey results confirmed these concerns, with several respondents noting that recycling capacity is currently too limited to meet ambitious quotas.

Here is noticeable how national differences stem from different levels of readiness. Strong infrastructure and regulatory alignment in Germany contrast with missing structural readiness in Italy and Spain.

Lessons learned across all sectors

Across countries, stakeholders noted that some instruments, especially taxation of virgin materials or carbon pricing face political resistance. In Germany and Italy industry representatives expressed concern about global competitiveness and consumer backlash. While in Spain and Slovakia responses indicated lower public acceptance for measures that increase consumer costs, given tighter household budgets. Likewise, in Netherlands and Belgium there was more openness to taxation in principle, although stakeholders stressed the need for EU-level coordination to avoid competitiveness distortions

From the analysis received from all sectors and countries analysed it is noted that regulatory ambition, anchored in criteria and standards, must be matched by capacity, finance, and acceptance strategies. Where these conditions were present, stakeholders converged on practical policy paths. If they were not, the same instruments were judged risky or unworkable. For policymakers and industry, the immediate opportunity is to combine targeted regulation, enabling finance, and implementation support along sector-specific roadmaps that turn national realities into investable certainty.

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ANNEX - Policy set per sector

The policy sets developed in work package 5 and presented to stakeholders during the DEPLOY conferences are consigned here below.

Chemical sector:

Policy Set	Circularity / toxicity		Policy Set	Biomass / GHG reduction		
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments		Direct regulation	Mixed policy approach	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy For developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD* framework and decontamination technologies <p>(* Safe and Sustainable by Design)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy For developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD* framework and decontamination technologies <p>(* Safe and Sustainable by Design)</p>	Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemicals production – leading to phase out of fossil feedstocks, e.g. in 2050 ➤ Additional: innovation subsidies for development and market penetration of non-fossil chemicals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Product subsidy for non-fossil chemicals, for example "green VAT" (reduced Value-Added Tax) ➤ Additional: phase out of fossil feedstocks leading to a final ban, e.g. in 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for innovative non-fossil chemicals, including supporting market penetration of novel products
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Thresholds for key Substances of Concern in products that inhibit reuse, recycling etc. ➤ REACH: extended criteria for chemicals permission that consider recycling, reuse etc. of products ➤ SCIP Extension Extension of EU SCIP database to chemicals inhibiting circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Pollution tax on key Substances of Concern that pose major risks to health or environment and thus inhibit circularity (e.g., lead, PFAS, flame retardants) 	Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Materials Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the subsidy (e.g., Renewable Materials Directive following the Renewable Energy Directive) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon tax for fossil feedstocks in chemicals production and for low-value biomass uses

Textile sector:

Policy Set	Circularity		Policy Set	Biomass	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments		Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota for use of recycled (and bio-based) material in textiles production and imports ➤ Ecodesign criteria for mandatory durability, reparability and recyclability standards (incl. for imports) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, including support for market penetration of innovative products ➤ "Green VAT" Reduced Value-Added Tax on re-used or recycled textiles 	Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota for use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock in textile production and imports ➤ Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles including support for market penetration of innovative products
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ban on Destruction of Unsold Goods (Existing EU instrument) as part of polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks in textiles production 	Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sustainability criteria for textiles to be eligible to the quota, public procurement (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Environmental tax on "fast fashion" textiles, fibers, yarns and fabrics (e.g., including for non-sustainable cotton products) to limit waste and pollution

Construction sector:

Policy Set	Circularity	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ecodesign criteria For building companies on design, construction and use of materials. Aim should be to design for reuse, disassembly, physical durability, adaptability and repair and minimising material intensity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for innovative circular technologies or practices (e.g., use of recycled materials)
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Demolition Standards Requirements for the demolition of buildings, that increase chances for re-use, upcycling and recycling of materials, and thus encourage waste reduction and possibly refurbishment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Material tax on the use of virgin raw materials for construction (e.g., gravel, stone, sand) including imports

Policy Set	Biomass	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota/target for use of biobased and recycled material in new buildings including higher targets for public procurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for development and uses of innovative bio-based construction materials
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sustainability criteria for biobased construction material to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) ➤ Subsidy for refurbishment of buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon tax on all lifecycle GHG emissions of building materials that are NOT part of current carbon pricing (EU-ETS I+II) including the carbon content of short-life biomass materials. ➤ Carbon credit / subsidy Bio-based building materials that ensure long-term storage of carbon (e.g., 50+ years) are exempt from the tax and receive a credit / subsidy.

Plastic sector:

Policy Set	Circularity	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota for use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.) ➤ Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products to improve ease of repair, recycling etc. ➤ Public procurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Product bans of additional single-use and short-life plastic products or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon price for use of fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics

Policy Set	Biomass	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria (↓) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sustainability criteria for receiving the product subsidy. E.g., mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc. ➤ Additional: Cap for share or total quantity of biomass used in the sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon tax on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use / non-durable bioplastics products

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